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INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

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Summary

This deliverable (D3.7) presents the testing and valorisation of the NOVASOIL toolbox, which integrates three digital instruments: the Digital Hub of Knowledge (DHK), the Digital Tool for Analysis (DTA), and the Decision Support Tool (DST). The aim is to assess their capacity to overcome social and economic barriers in implementing soil health business models (SHBMs) across Europe.

Testing was carried out with farmers, landowners, and stakeholders in nine partner countries through case studies and Communities of Practice (CoP). The evaluation covered three main dimensions: (i) economic impact on costs and income, (ii) ecological performance using Life Cycle Analysis (LCA), and (iii) user perceptions regarding clarity, usability, and usefulness.

Key findings include:

- **Economic impact:** In most case studies, the DTA demonstrated the strongest potential to reduce variable costs and increase farm income (e.g., in Latvia and Germany), though high initial investment remains a barrier. In contrast, vineyards in Bulgaria achieved climate-positive outcomes with net CO₂ sequestration of **-0.4 t CO₂eq/ha/year**, showing that some SHBMs can generate both economic and environmental benefits.
- **Ecological performance:** LCA results revealed wide variability. Vineyards (Bulgaria) and alfalfa (Italy) showed low emissions (<2 t CO₂eq/ha/year), while tomatoes (Italy) reached high levels (>5 t CO₂eq/ha/year) due to intensive input use. This highlights the importance of crop choice and input management for sustainable soil strategies.
- **User evaluation:** Across all CoP, the DHK was seen as the most user-friendly tool, DTA as the most economically valuable, and DST as the most strategic for long-term planning. Stakeholders emphasized that **integration of all three tools** is essential — no single tool can meet the diverse needs of SHBMs.

Overall, the NOVASOIL toolbox provides a **comprehensive digital framework** to support sustainable, resilient, and inclusive soil management. The tools hold strong potential for integration into EU agricultural policies, including CAP subsidy assessments, advisory services, and soil carbon farming initiatives.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context of WP 3 objectives

Work Package 3 (WP3) focuses on the testing and development of a digital toolbox designed to incentivize and support soil health business models (SHBMs). Its core objective is to evaluate how digital solutions can help overcome the **social, economic, and ecological barriers** that currently hinder the adoption of sustainable soil management practices across Europe.

Specifically, WP3 seeks to:

- **Demonstrate practical value** of the three NOVASOIL tools—Digital Hub of Knowledge (DHK), Digital Tool for Analysis (DTA), and Decision Support Tool (DST)—in reducing costs, increasing income, and facilitating ecosystem service delivery.
- **Test scalability and adaptability** of these tools across diverse European contexts (agriculture, forestry, and multifunctional land use systems).
- **Bridge science, policy, and practice** by aligning tool functions with the **10 objectives of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP 2023–2027)**, ensuring direct relevance to EU policy frameworks.
- **Enhance stakeholder engagement** through the active involvement of farmers, landowners, and Communities of Practice (CoP), ensuring that tools are user-driven and context-sensitive.

In this sense, WP3 is not only a technical validation exercise but also a **strategic step towards mainstreaming SHBMs** within EU policies and markets. By integrating economic, ecological, and social perspectives, the toolbox aims to provide a solid foundation for scaling up soil health practices across Europe, thereby supporting the **EU Green Deal, Farm-to-Fork Strategy, and Mission Soil objectives**.

1.2 Connection with the other WPs

The development and validation of the NOVASOIL toolbox in WP3 is strongly interconnected with the other work packages of the project. Knowledge flows across WPs ensure that the tools are not developed in isolation but are grounded in scientific evidence, tested in real contexts, and aligned with policy needs.

- **WP1 (Framework and stakeholder needs):** provides the initial mapping of soil health challenges, barriers, and incentives across Europe. These insights form the foundation for defining the design requirements of the toolbox tools.
- **WP2 (Business model development):** supplies case-specific business models and innovative practices that serve as testbeds for WP3. This ensures that the tools are validated in realistic socio-economic and ecological settings.

- **WP3 (Toolbox testing and development):** builds directly on WP1 and WP2, transforming conceptual insights into practical digital solutions and testing their applicability across multiple contexts.
- **WP4 (Evisoning incentives & Policy Solutions):** relies on WP3 outputs to develop actionable guidelines and policy recommendations, ensuring that NOVASOIL results have long-term impact in EU soil health strategies.
- **WP5 (Dissemination and exploitation):** ensures that the tested toolbox is communicated to farmers, landowners, policymakers, and other stakeholders through Communities of Practice (CoP), advisory networks, and policy dialogues. Feedback from WP5 further refines the usability and policy relevance of the tools.

In summary, WP3 acts as the **“bridge” between conceptual design and real-world application**, linking stakeholder needs (WP1), innovative business models (WP2), and policy integration (WP4–WP5). This interconnected approach ensures that the NOVASOIL toolbox is scientifically robust, user-driven, and policy-relevant.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the document

Deliverable D 3.7 Report on testing and Valorisation of the toolbox instruments aims to present overall update on its progress carried out under T 3.4: Testing and Valorisation of the toolbox instruments” in the framework of WP3 "Testing and development of a toolbox for incentives" under the NOVASOIL project.

In Task 3.4, farmers, landowners, and stakeholders within the NOVASOIL CoP assess these tools to address the delivery of various ecosystem services (e.g., carbon capture, clean water, clean air, and biodiversity), which depend on a full set of functions that define social preferences and the confluence of different pressures. The ecological and human impact of soil health business models was evaluated using the FaST platform for life-cycle analysis (LCA). In cooperation with Work Package 5, we considered national specificities and helped develop a usage strategy within their specific economic and policy/contractual relationships. This task involves collecting internal feedback on the evaluated solutions and case studies. It also involves addressing the perceived usefulness of soil health business models and the cost of implementation in relation to the characteristics of different land uses, such as agriculture, forestry, and urban areas.

In general, the WP3 focuses on a toolbox development. It contains three major components (fig. 1). The final version of the first tool – digital hub of knowledge (Tool 1 - DHK) – was presented in Deliverable D 3.5 Report on final version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models (Nikolov et al. 2024b).

The final version of the second tool – Digital tools for analysis for soil health business models (Tool 2 - DTA) – is presented in D3.8 Report on final version of tools for analysis of the soil health business models (Nikolov et. al. 2025).

The preliminary version of the third component of the toolbox is presented in Deliverable D 3.6 Preliminary version on decision support tool for soil health business models (Nikolov et al. 2024c). The tool 3 is called Decision support tool for soil health business models (Tool 3 - DST). The report for the final version will be submitted on the month 36.

Figure 1 NOVASOIL digital toolbox

1.4 Process of development

The overall process of development of D3.7 included several steps:

First, It has been developed a three-step methodology to estimate how the application of digital tools (DHK, DTA, and DST) could impact variable costs and income, thereby supporting the effort to overcome the barriers for application soil health business models; it has been developed an AHP survey to assess their potential to support the delivery of various ecosystem services and It has been made an evaluation of the digital tools according to the confluence of different pressures. For this purpose, a file with instructions and survey has been send to the partners on 04.02.2025.

Second, an instruction for conducting a Life-Cycle Analysis (LCA) was creating. It was sent to the partners on 23.05.2025.

Third, for the purpose of the feedback from CoP was created a document that gives information to CoP about the digital solutions in NOVASOIL toolbox, summary of the results from testing and valorisation considering national specificities, business models and case studies. The CoP members in each NOVASOIL partner country had to complete a short survey for evaluation NOVASOIL toolbox. The email with the survey was sent on 29.05.2025.

2 Policy brief

The analysis of digital tools by business model type reveals consistent patterns that highlight their importance for sustainable land management and soil health promotion.

2.1 Analysis of the NOVASOIL toolbox in terms of business models

In the value chain business model, Digital Tools for Analysis (DTA) emerges as a key driver for reshaping cost structures and increasing long-term income. Although the initial investment is seen as a barrier in Bulgaria and Latvia, in Spain DTA contributes to efficiency gains and reduced variable costs. Income growth is strongly linked to improved soil quality and climate adaptation. While not all benefits are immediate, DTA provides strategic value by enabling a gradual transition toward more resilient and market-oriented agricultural systems.

Decision Support Tool (DST) plays a leading role across countries, especially in planning and resource management. Hubs of Knowledge (DHK) are essential for stakeholder engagement and capacity building, while DTA supports monitoring and adaptability. All countries stress the need for integrated use of the three types of tools—no single tool is sufficient on its own. Spain places the strongest emphasis on DST, Latvia highlights knowledge and community aspects, and Bulgaria takes a balanced approach.

In the agricultural production/value chain model, DTA proves beneficial by reducing costs and increasing income in areas such as soil quality improvement, biodiversity preservation, and water cycle regulation. Although it has a limited influence on long-term return, it delivers long-term strategic benefits. Both DST and DTA are essential for ecosystem services delivery. While Hubs of Knowledge play a secondary role, they are still preferred for addressing certain social challenges.

Under the collective and value chain business model, the impact of DTA varies depending on context. In one Italian case, DTA increases income without affecting costs, while in another, sustainable practices raise both. The tools address a range of economic, environmental, and social services. Hubs of Knowledge are especially effective for tackling social pressures, Digital Tools for environmental monitoring, and DST for land management and water use.

For the agricultural production business model, DTA lowers costs and boosts income in several key areas, although it does not affect long-term return. Both DST and DTA are essential for environmental care, while Hubs of Knowledge play a limited role in this context. However, they are valuable in addressing social barriers such as poverty and education.

In the forest business model, DTA helps reduce operational costs and supports income growth through improved practices—particularly related to soil quality. However, climate change actions may raise costs without direct income benefits. DHK stands out as the most impactful tool for natural resource protection and community engagement. The Digital Tool is effective

for monitoring and planning, while the DST supports governance and environmental strategies.

In summary, all business models highlight the need for combined use of all three tools. DTA stands out for its economic potential, DST for strategic planning, and Hubs of Knowledge for long-term social transformation. Together, they offer a comprehensive digital framework to support sustainable, resilient, and inclusive land use practices.

2.2. LCA analysis per country

The Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) results from five farms in Italy, Spain, Germany, and Bulgaria offer valuable insight into the carbon footprint of diverse agricultural systems. All farms (beside Bulgaria) assessed fall within the medium carbon impact range—between 1 and 4 tons of CO₂-equivalent per hectare per year—yet their emission profiles differ significantly based on crop type, management practices, and local conditions.

In Italy (District of the Sands, Collective and value chain), the farm grows multiple crops and demonstrates wide variation in emissions. Alfalfa performs best, with emissions at just 2.32 t CO₂-eq/ha, largely due to its low-input, rainfed, and no-till cultivation without nitrogen fertilization. Tomatoes, however, exhibit the highest emissions of all systems analyzed, at 5.33 t CO₂-eq/ha—exceeding the medium impact threshold—mainly due to heavy fertilizer and pesticide use. Maize and wheat remain within the medium range (3.37 and 3.69 t CO₂-eq/ha, respectively) but are relatively high, mostly due to nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions and limited soil carbon sequestration.

Italy's second farm (A model for multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas, Collective and value chain) compares conventional and organic wheat soil strategy. Both fall within the medium impact category, with the conventional system emitting 1.35 t CO₂-eq/ha and the organic system 1.70 t CO₂-eq/ha—about 26% higher. Although the organic production avoids synthetic inputs, it still emits more N₂O due to manure use. Moreover, lower yields in the organic production result in higher emission intensity per ton of product (415 kg CO₂-eq/t vs. 306 kg CO₂-eq/t in the conventional production), suggesting that sustainability benefits in organic production may be offset by efficiency losses.

In Spain (Integrated production, Value chain), olive cultivation emits 1.67 t CO₂-eq/ha/year, placing it comfortably within the medium range. Though the soil strategy includes irrigation and fertilization, its overall emissions remain moderate. However, the most concerning factor is the significant loss of soil organic carbon (1.17 t CO₂-eq/ha), which compromises long-term sustainability unless soil conservation measures are prioritized.

Germany's (CO₂-Land, Agricultural Production/ Value chain) no-till wheat soil strategy emits 2.90 t CO₂-eq/ha/year, despite conservation practices like reduced tillage and residue incorporation. The primary emissions source is nitrogen fertilizer use, both from direct field emissions and the upstream

production process. This case illustrates that even advanced, mechanized soil strategy can have relatively high emissions if nitrogen management is not optimized.

In Bulgaria (Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism, Value chain), the vineyard soil strategy represented shows a positive carbon balance, with a net sequestration rate of 0.4 tCO₂eq/ha/year. This places the farm within the low-emission or even climate-positive category, meaning it acts as a carbon sink rather than a source. This is a highly favorable outcome from a climate mitigation perspective.

The following elements likely contribute to this positive performance: Perennial vegetation (vineyards) helps maintain continuous ground cover and carbon sequestration. No emissions are reported from land-use change, which avoids large upfront carbon losses. No forest area is impacted, and there's no indication of deforestation or degradation. Presumably low levels of disturbance and biomass loss, since no values are reported there.

In conclusion, while most farms operate within the same emission category, their performance in terms of carbon efficiency and sustainability differs greatly. Orchards like vineyards, as well as low-input crops such as alfalfa, demonstrate strong climate performance. In contrast, input-intensive crops like tomatoes or wheat grown under high nitrogen regimes show higher emissions both per hectare and per unit of output. Compared to farms in different BMs in Italy, Spain, and Germany, where emissions range from 1.35 to 5.33 tCO₂eq/ha/year, this vineyard clearly outperforms in terms of carbon efficiency. It joins the Bulgarian vineyard in the earlier analysis as an example of climate-smart viticulture, capable of both agricultural production and net carbon sequestration.

2.3. CoP evaluation of NOVASOIL toolbox

The NOVASOIL Toolbox, consisting of three digital tools (DHK, DTA, and DST), was assessed across CoP in partner countries for clarity, usability, usefulness, and policy relevance.

DHK is widely appreciated for its clear structure and informative content. Users value its strong foundation in soil health knowledge, particularly as an accessible entry point for farmers and practitioners. It is recognized as the most user-friendly tool, offering a smooth experience that can be further enhanced with improved content organization and clearer formatting.

DTA stood out as the most valuable tool for soil health business models, especially in agricultural production. When accessible, it was praised for its ability to guide decision-making and optimize resource use. Stakeholders viewed these as solvable and were confident in the tool's strong long-term utility.

DST was acknowledged for its advanced analytical capabilities and potential to support detailed field-level assessments. While more complex, it holds

strong promise for expert users and researchers, and with improved explanations and simplified language, it can be made more accessible to a broader audience.

Across all tools, participants highlighted the benefit of integrating them into agricultural policy and education. They recommended their use in CAP-related subsidy assessments, advisory services, and training programs, emphasizing the tools' potential to improve digital literacy and soil stewardship across rural communities. The suggestion to implement pilot farms and demonstration projects further reflects confidence in the tools' real-world applicability.

3 Testing and valorization

3.1 Methodology

To understand how the digital tools developed in task 3.1, task 3.3 and t 3.5 can help overcome the social and economic barriers to implementing soil health business models, a three-step methodology has been developed. This methodology begins with the identification of the main incentive for each case, as presented in the D3.4 Report on New Incentives Soil Health Business Models. It then proceeds to identify and evaluate the related opportunities using BOCR (Benefits, Opportunities, Costs, and Risks) analysis. From the full list of opportunities, only those with significant economic and social relevance—as identified by stakeholders—are selected. The lack of progress in applying these opportunities and achieving related economic and social development is considered a key barrier to improved soil health management. For the testing and valorisation phase, stakeholders assess how the application of DTA could impact variable costs and income, thereby supporting the effort to overcome these barriers (table 2).

Table 1: Estimate how DTA for every Barrier/factor will affect variable costs and income for your case study

Barriers/factors	Influence on variable costs			Influence on income		
	Decrease	No impact	Increase	Decrease	No impact	Increase
Barrier 1						
Barrier 2						
...						
Barrier n						

Place “x” on every row once for variable costs and once for income.

The second step in the methodology involves the evaluation of the following three digital instruments:

- DHK: Digital Hub of Knowledge
- DTA: Digital Tool for Analysis
- DST: Decision Support Tool

These tools are assessed for their potential to support the delivery of various ecosystem services (such as carbon sequestration, clean water, clean air, biodiversity), based on a set of functions that reflect social preferences.

The analysis begins by referring to the strategic criteria defined in Deliverable D3.4. Each partner, based on the specific characteristics of their business model and case, selects strategic objectives that align with the policy goals of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). These objectives are drawn from the 10 CAP objectives (2023–2027), listed below:

1. Ensure a fair income for farmers
2. Increase competitiveness
3. Improve the position of farmers in the food chain
4. Climate change action
5. Environmental care
6. Preserve landscapes and biodiversity
7. Support generational renewal
8. Promote vibrant rural areas
9. Protect food and health quality
10. Foster knowledge and innovation

Depending on the business model, each case study selects 3 to 4 CAP objectives that are most relevant to their context.

These CAP objectives are strongly interconnected with ecosystem services, and for this reason, relevant case studies and selected CAP goals are mapped against specific ecosystem services.

1. Climate change action is related to climate regulation and carbon storage ecosystem services.
2. Environmental care is linked to air quality, soil quality, and water quality ecosystem services.
3. Preserving landscapes and biodiversity is associated with landscape and scenery, as well as biodiversity ecosystem services.
4. Supporting generational renewal is connected to recreational access and improvements to physical and mental health ecosystem services.
5. Vibrant rural areas are related to the preservation of cultural heritage ecosystem service.
6. Protecting food and health quality is linked to quality and security products, and farm animal health and welfare ecosystem services.

Digital tools were assessed for their contribution to each CAP objective separately using multicriteria analysis, analytic hierarchy process (AHP) analyses that have been prepared for every case.

- **AHP**

In order to create the methodology of multicriteria analysis the assessment criteria have to be set. It is used 5 principles for sustainability in food and agriculture denoted in FAO (2014) article to determine the assessment criteria which also reflect social preferences. Each case has selected CAP objectives. In order to estimate how DTs can influence CAP objectives we will create an AHP questionnaire for every CAP objectives related with the case (table 3).

Estimation goal: **Assessment of the DTs according CAP objectives**

Table 2: List of criteria and short names

Principles/criteria	Short name
Improving efficiency in the use of resources is crucial to sustainable agriculture	Use of resources
Sustainability requires direct action to conserve, protect and enhance natural resources	Natural resources protection
Agriculture that fails to protect and improve rural livelihoods, equity and social well-being is unsustainable	Improve rural livelihoods
Enhanced resilience of people, communities and ecosystems is key to sustainable agriculture	Resilience of ecosystems
Sustainable food and agriculture requires responsible and effective governance mechanisms	Governance mechanisms

Alternatives represent the objects of evaluation, which in our case are the three digital tools.

- DHK: Digital Hub of Knowledge
- DTA: Digital Tool for Analysis
- DST: Decision Support Tool

The third step of the methodology is the evaluation of the digital tools according to the *confluence of different pressures*. To achieve this, the

partners ranked the tools based on their specific case study and in relation to each individual *confluence of pressure* using the table 4.

Table 3: Rank by placing a number from 1 to 3 for each DT according to each pressure where 1 means it ranks highest and 3 - the lowest.

Answer every row.

Pressures	Hub of knowledge	Digital tool for analysis	Decision support tool
Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition			
Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns			
Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion			
Water scarcity and pollution			
Loss of living resources and biodiversity			
Climate change			
Stagnation in agricultural research			

3.2 Country analysis

The upcoming analysis explored business models across partner countries. It will follow a common structure to ensure comparability, focusing on three main areas.

3.2.1 Bulgaria case study

Business model name: Integrated production in the vineyards with winery and rural tourism

Business model type: Value chain

Business model type of the Bulgarian case is Value chain. It is related to management of the viticulture potential of the country and exercises control over the rights for planting new vineyards, replanting and eradication of vineyards. The effective functioning of the value chain in recent years leads to the improvement and stabilization of the sector, increasing the quality and competitiveness of Bulgarian wines, both on the domestic and foreign markets. The aim of the Program for local traditional and regional traditional products for the period 2021–2023 is to value the potential of local traditional and regional traditional products in the wine sector and strengthen their relationship with communities to develop the local economy and agricultural sector. Local traditional and regional traditional products give Bulgarian citizens and guests of the country a variety of tastes, quality, touch with culture and traditions and life of the local economy and communities.

Analysis of social and/or economic barriers

DTA effects on variable costs and income for each barrier/factor is summarized below (table 5), resulting in the following key points:

- Initial investment is perceived as a major **cost-increasing factor** (5 out of 6) and a potential **income reducer** (4 out of 6), making it the most critical short-term barrier to adoption.
- While its impact on cost reduction is moderate, it is strongly associated with increased income (4 out of 6), highlighting its value as a strategic, long-term benefit.
- Improvements in soil quality are universally seen as beneficial, with costs decreasing (5 votes) and income increasing (6 votes).

Table 4: DTA analysis of social and/or economic barriers through variable costs and income

Barriers/factors	Influence on variable costs			Influence on income		
	Decrease	No impact	Increase	Decrease	No impact	Increase
Initial costs	0	1	5	4	1	1
Long term results in food security	3	2	1	0	2	4
Soil quality	5	0	1	0	0	6

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver Environmental care ecosystem service

In the context of the business model *"Integrated production in the vineyards with winery and rural tourism"*, and *"Environmental care"* ecosystem service the application of different tools for supporting soil health within sustainable agriculture shows varied strengths for. For improving resource efficiency in vineyard production management, DST (39.0%) are seen as most effective. Protection of soil and natural resources aligns closely with DTA (39.0%). Addressing unsustainable practices—such as neglecting soil management that impacts rural livelihoods—is where DST (53.7%) again take precedence. Enhancing resilience in the vineyard ecosystem, especially where tourism and production intersect, is best supported through a DHK (53.7%), promoting education on sustainable practices among farmers and visitors alike. For governance mechanisms—like land use planning or environmental compliance in the vineyard setting—DST (49.0%) play a critical role.

DST are seen as the most valuable overall (37.7%)—especially for governance, resource efficiency, and addressing unsustainable practices in agriculture. DHK is especially important for building resilience in communities and

ecosystems, showing the value of shared learning and education. DTA has high influence in areas involving resource conservation but are generally rated lower than the other tools across most categories. The distribution of preferences shows that no single tool dominates all areas, indicating a need for a balanced, integrated approach that combines knowledge, analytics, and decision-making capabilities.

Figure 2. Result of the assessment of DT's according "Environmental care" criteria

Assessing of the toolbox tools to delivery of CAP goal - To preserve landscapes and biodiversity and landscape and scenery and biodiversity ecosystem service

In the context of the Bulgarian case study, business model (BM) "Integrated production in the vineyards with winery and rural tourism", aimed at preserving landscapes and biodiversity while supporting soil health, the data highlights a strong preference for DST in several key areas. These tools are especially valued for improving resource efficiency (53.9%), supporting sustainable governance (53.9%), and guiding direct conservation actions (49.0%). In contrast, when the focus shifts to social sustainability—such as protecting rural livelihoods—hubs of knowledge dominate (70.3%), emphasizing the importance of shared expertise and local engagement. DTA are most appreciated when enhancing ecosystem and community resilience (41.1%), suggesting their strength lies in monitoring and adapting to changes in complex vineyard environments. The final results reflect DST as the most effective (41.9%), followed by hubs of knowledge (31.4%) and digital tools (26.7%).

DST are essential for guiding soil health practices that align with landscape and biodiversity preservation, particularly in areas of governance, resource efficiency, and conservation planning. Hubs of Knowledge play a key role in fostering social well-being and sustainable livelihoods within vineyard communities. DTA are most effective in tracking ecological resilience and should be integrated for adaptive vineyard and tourism management. The varied preferences indicate that a synergistic approach—using all three tools in combination—can best support soil health and sustainable development in multifunctional landscapes like vineyards.

Figure 3. Result of the assessment of DT's according "To preserve landscapes and biodiversity" criteria

Assessing the toolbox tools to delivery of CAP goal - To protect food and health quality and connected - quality and security products, and farm animal health and welfare ecosystem service

In the context of the Bulgarian case study, BM "Integrated production in the vineyards with winery and rural tourism", focused on protecting food and health quality through soil health, the data reveals a leading role for DHK across most categories. Hubs of knowledge are especially emphasized in relation to social sustainability (62.3%) and responsible governance (42.9%), underlying the importance of shared learning and collective action in vineyard and rural development. DTA are most valuable for improving efficiency (31.2%) and are equally matched with hubs of knowledge in enhancing resilience (40.0%), pointing to their role in monitoring and adaptive vineyard practices. DST rank highest when it comes to optimizing resource use (49.0%) and are tied with hubs of knowledge in supporting governance (42.9%), proving

essential for data-driven planning and soil management strategies. Overall, the final evaluation ranks DHK as the most effective tool (44.7%), followed by DST (31.7%) and DTA (23.6%).

DHK emerges as the most valuable tool for preserving food and health quality through soil health, particularly in supporting livelihoods, governance, and sustainability awareness. DST remain crucial for efficiency and strategic planning, while DTA add value in resilience-building and resource monitoring. These findings highlight the need for a complementary approach that integrates knowledge sharing, decision-making frameworks, and analytical tools for sustainable vineyard management and rural tourism development.

Figure 4. Result of the assessment of DT's according "To protect food and health quality" criteria

Analysis of confluence of different pressures

In the Bulgarian case study, BM "Integrated production in the vineyards with winery and rural tourism", addressing key pressures on soil health reveals varied strengths of the three tools—DHK, DTA, and DST. The DHK is considered most effective in tackling challenges like poverty, unsustainable consumption, soil depletion, and stagnation in research, pointing to the need for shared learning and community capacity-building. DTA are rated highest in understanding the complexities of inadequate diets, land degradation, and biodiversity loss, showcasing their role in providing precise data for informed interventions. Meanwhile, DST are particularly valuable in managing water scarcity and planning for research investment, showing their strength in technical and strategic decision-making.

Hubs of Knowledge are vital for raising awareness, improving education, and driving community-led action against poverty, soil decline, and weak research systems. DTA offer crucial insights for monitoring ecological pressures such as biodiversity loss and consumption trends. DST are key in managing water resources and guiding adaptive planning. A combined use of these tools is essential for holistic and effective soil health management within the integrated vineyard and tourism landscape.

Table 5: Ranking the DT's according different pressures

Pressures	Hub of knowledge	Digital tool for analysis	Decision support tool
Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition	2	2	1
Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns	1	3	2
Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion	2	3	1
Water scarcity and pollution	1	2	3
Loss of living resources and biodiversity	3	1	2
Climate change	1	2	2
Stagnation in agricultural research	1	2	3

3.2.2 Estonia case study

Business model name: Crop production

Business model type: Agricultural production

ETKI is a state research and development institute in the area of governance of the Estonian Ministry of Rural Affairs. Among others, ETKI research impact of catch crops, tillage technologies and fertilizing on soil physical, chemical and biological properties. The crop production technologies and machinery use are analyzed to assess their impact on the environment and farms economy. ETKI cooperates with other organizations, which are developing digital maps based on soil properties. These tools help to choose crops on fields, show fields soil texture, carbon stock, moisture level or erosion level. The usability of these digital maps to develop new business models aiming at adding value to soil conservation should be investigated.

Analysis of social and/or economic barriers

Estimation how DTA for every Barrier/factor will affect variable costs and income for Estonian case study shows the following:

- Initial costs of investment is perceived as a major **cost-decreasing factor** and a potential **income reducer**, making it the most critical short-term for DTA as a barrier to adoption.
- While DTA impact on long term return is a decreasing factor for variable costs, it is strongly associated with increased income, highlighting its value as a strategic, long-term benefit.

- Sustainable crop production and Food demand are other two factors which have the same influence on increasing variable costs and income.
- Long term results in food security have a negative effect over variable costs and income
- DTA has no influence on Climate change, and Soil quality.

Table 6: Analysis of social and/or economic barriers through variable costs and income

Barriers/factors	Influence on variable costs			Influence on income		
	Decrease	No impact	Increase	Decrease	No impact	Increase
Initial costs	x			x		
Long term return	x					x
Sustainable crop production			x			x
Food demand			x			x
Long term results in food security			x	x		
Climate change		x			x	
Soil quality		x			x	

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver Fostering knowledge ecosystem service

In the context of the Estonian case study, business model "Crop production", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection of Fostering knowledge (ecosystem service) sustainable crop production shows varied strengths. The DST emerge as the most influential in resource use efficiency (64.7%) and in improving rural livelihoods (63.8%), also performing well in overall final results (33.8%), highlighting their strategic role in guiding farm-level decision-making and addressing unsustainable practices. The DHK stands out in supporting ecosystem resilience (54.8%) and natural resource protection (54.8%), as well as being the top tool for enhancing governance mechanisms (45.4%). This reflects its value in promoting shared learning, fostering stakeholder collaboration, and strengthening community-based approaches. The DTA plays a meaningful role, particularly in

governance mechanisms (32.1%) and resource conservation (21.1–27.7%), though it generally scores lower than the other tools in most categories.

The final distribution of preferences (38.1% for DTA, 33.8% for DST, 28.1% for DHK) confirms that no single tool is dominant across all dimensions. Instead, the findings emphasize the importance of a balanced, integrated approach, combining knowledge transfer, data analysis, and structured decision-making. Such synergistic use of the tools can better support complex sustainability goals—like soil health, biodiversity, and rural development—while aligning with CAP priorities.

Fostering knowledge ecosystem service

Figure 5. Result of the assessment of DT's according to Fostering knowledge ecosystem services

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver “To improve the position of farmers in the food chain” ecosystem service

In the context of the Estonian case study, business model "Crop production", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection of improvement the position of farmers in the food chain (ecosystem service) sustainable crop production shows varied strengths.

DST is especially valued for improving resource efficiency (62.6%) and improvement of rural livelihoods (50.0%). In contrast, when the focus shifts to resilience to ecosystems (68.1%), natural resource protection (70.4%) and governance mechanisms (60.8%) hubs of knowledge dominate. DTA are not preferred in connection within this ecosystem service. The final results reflect

hubs of knowledge as the most effective (40.5%), DST (39.8%), followed by and DTA (19.8%).

DST are essential for improvement the position of farmers in the food chain guiding use of resources that align with improvement rural livelihoods. Hubs of Knowledge play a key role in improvement natural resource protection, resilience of ecosystems and governance mechanism. DTA is not preferable for improvement the position of farmers in the food chain.

Figure 6. Result of the assessment of DT's according "To improve the position of farmers in the food chain" criteria

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver "To protect food and health quality" ecosystem service

In the context of the Estonian case study, business model "Crop production", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection to protect food and health quality (ecosystem service) sustainable crop production shows similar influence.

DHK dominate in governance mechanisms (66.5%). DTA is preferred in connection within use of resources (41.1%). The results reflect hubs of knowledge as the most effective (40.9%), followed by DST (32.2%), and DTA (26.9%).

Hubs of Knowledge play a key role in governance mechanism and also in the rest of the criterias. The rest of the Digital tools are preferable with equal level for protection food and health quality as ecosystem service.

Figure 7. Result of the assessment of DT's

Analysis of delivery of various ecosystem services which depends on a full set of functions defining social preferences and confluence of different pressures.

In the context of the Estonian case study, business model "Crop production", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection sustainable crop production shows similar influence of the three digital tools—DHK, DTA, and DST.

The DHK is not considered as a most effective tool.

DTA are rated highest in understanding the complexities of Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition, Inadequate diets and Water scarcity and pollution, showcasing their role in providing precise data for informed interventions.

Meanwhile, DST are particularly valuable in Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion, Loss of living resources and biodiversity, Climate change and Stagnation in agricultural research showing their strength in technical and strategic decision-making.

DHK is not preferable for the business model "Crop production". DTA is important to overcome the next three pressures: Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition, inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns and Water scarcity and pollution. The most important tool is DST which is key

in Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion, Loss of living resources and biodiversity, Climate change and Stagnation in agricultural research.

Table 7: Ranking the DT's according to different pressures

Pressures	Hub of knowledge	Digital tool for analysis	Decision support tool
Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition	2	3	1
Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns	1	3	2
Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion	2	1	3
Water scarcity and pollution	2	3	1
Loss of living resources and biodiversity	1	2	3
Climate change	1	2	3
Stagnation in agricultural research	1	2	3

3.2.3 Germany case study

Business model name: name CO2-Land

Business model type: type Agricultural production/value chain

Analysis of social and/or economic barriers

Estimation how DTA for every Barrier/factor will affect variable costs and income for German case study shows the following:

- Long term return, Sustainable crop production, Food demand and Biodiversity preservation are barriers for which DTA has no influence on variable costs in a CO2-Land business model. From these four barriers long term return and Sustainable crop production impose over increasing income. The rest two have no income impact.
- While DTA impact on Soil quality is decreasing factor for variable costs, it is strongly associated with increased income, highlighting its value as a strategic, long-term benefit.
- DTA has influence on Climate change as decreasing variable costs and income increasing.

Table 8: DTA analysis of social and/or economic barriers through variable costs and income

Barriers/factors	Influence on variable costs			Influence on income		
	Decreases	No impact	Increases	Decreases	No impact	Increases

Long term return		x				x
Sustainable crop production		x				x
Food demand		x			x	
Biodiversity preservation		x			x	
Climate change			x		x	
Soil quality	x					x

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver Climate change ecosystem service

In the context of the German case study, business model "CO2-Land", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection of Climate change (ecosystem service) sustainable crop production shows varied strengths.

DST is especially valued for improving resource efficiency (67.5%), improvement of rural livelihoods (56.9%) and resilience of ecosystems (55.7%). In contrast, when the focus shifts to natural resource protection (53.9%) and governance mechanisms (62.3%) DTA dominate. DHK is not preferred in connection within this ecosystem service. The results reflect DTA as the most effective (44.3%), DST (42.2%), followed by DHK (13.5%).

DST are essential for Climate change guiding use of resources that align with improvement rural livelihoods and resilience of ecosystems. DTA plays a key role in improvement natural resource protection and governance mechanism. DHK is not preferable for Climate change.

Figure 8. Result of the assessment of DT's according "Climate change" criteria

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver Environmental care ecosystem service

In the context of the German case study, business model "CO₂-Land", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection of Environmental care (ecosystem service) sustainable crop production shows varied strengths.

DST is especially valued for improving resource efficiency (65.6%), natural resources protection (55.7%) and resilience of ecosystems (40.0%). In contrast, when the focus shifts to improve rural livelihoods (55.7%) and governance mechanisms (63.9%) DTA dominate. DHK is not preferred in connection within this ecosystem service. The final results reflect DST as the most effective (45.6%), DTA (39.3%), followed by DHK (15.1%).

DST for business model "CO₂-Land" is essential for Environmental care guiding use of resources that align with natural resources and resilience of ecosystems. DTA plays a key role in improvement rural livelihoods and governance mechanism. DHK is not preferable for Environmental care.

Figure 9. Result of the assessment of DTs according "Environmental care" criteria

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver Fostering knowledge ecosystem service

In the context of the German case study, business model "CO₂-Land", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection of Fostering knowledge (ecosystem service) sustainable crop production shows varied strengths.

The DHK emerges as the most effective overall (56.5%), particularly dominating in governance mechanisms (66.7%) and resilience of ecosystems (40%), where its strengths in stakeholder engagement, education, and capacity building are most impactful. It also plays a leading role in improving rural livelihoods (60%), highlighting its social relevance in fostering inclusive development and community well-being.

The DST is particularly effective in resource use (72.3%) and ecosystem resilience (40%), supporting evidence-based agricultural planning and sustainable land use. It also contributes to the results (24.6%), reinforcing its operational importance, though slightly trailing the Hub in overall perception.

The DTA ranks lower across most categories, with its highest impact in natural resources protection (17.4%) and governance mechanisms (16.7%). Despite its lower scores, its analytical value remains essential for monitoring and strategic feedback.

The combined insights confirm that no single tool is sufficient on its own. A complementary approach—leveraging the educational strength of the Hub, the planning power of DST, and the analytical capabilities of Digital Tools is necessary.

Figure 10. Result of the assessment of DT's according "Fostering knowledge" criteria

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver To ensure a fair income for farmers ecosystem service

The data presented highlights how the three toolbox tools contribute to the ecosystem service "To ensure a fair income for farmers", emphasizing their varying strengths. The DST stands out in use of resources (53.9%) and contributes significantly to natural resources protection (14.3%) and governance mechanisms (16.7%), confirming its role in improving farm-level decision-making and optimizing productivity for income stability.

The DTA is particularly effective in supporting resilience of ecosystems (53.9%), showcasing its ability to inform adaptive practices that indirectly stabilize income through environmental sustainability. It also plays a valuable role in use of resources (29.7%) and has a high overall performance (42.6%), underlining its importance in delivering evidence-based insights that enhance profitability.

The DHK, while less dominant in most categories, plays a supportive role in governance mechanisms (16.7%) and ecosystem resilience (29.7%), promoting learning and capacity building—especially relevant for long-term income

security. Interestingly, both the DTA and the DST are equally favored (44.4%) in improving rural livelihoods, further reinforcing their practical impact on economic well-being.

The result shows a relatively balanced appreciation for the DTA (42.6%) and DST (37.6%).

Figure 11. Result of the assessment of DT's according "To ensure a fair income for farmers" criteria

Analysis of delivery of various ecosystem services which depends on a full set of functions defining social preferences and confluence of different pressures.

In the context of the German case study, business model "CO2-Land", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection sustainable crop production shows similar influence of the three digital tools—DHK, DTA, and DST.

The DHK is not considered as a most effective tool.

DTA are rated highest in understanding the complexities Land scarcity, degradation.

Meanwhile, DST is the most preferable for the rest 5 pressures: Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition, Inadequate diets, Water scarcity and pollution and Loss of living resources and biodiversity.

DHK is preferable for Climate change for the business model "Crop production". DTA is important to overcome the Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion. The most important tool is DST which is key in following barriers: Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition, Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns, Water scarcity and pollution, Loss of living resources and biodiversity and Stagnation in agricultural research.

Table 9: Ranking the DT's according to different pressures

Pressures	Hub of knowledge	Digital tool for analysis	Decision support tool
Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition	1	2	3
Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns	1	2	3
Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion	2	3	1
Water scarcity and pollution	2	1	3
Loss of living resources and biodiversity	2	1	3
Climate change	3	1	2
Stagnation in agricultural research	1	2	3

3.2.4 Italian case study 1

Business model name: Multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas

Business model type: Collective and value chain

The case study derives from an integrated supply chain project funded in the framework of EU's Rural Development Policy, which involved research centers, private companies, farmers, and public administrations, to drive force of rural sustainable development through new cropping systems and management innovations. The internal and hilly areas of Tuscany Region are marginal areas characterized by conventional extensive agriculture and little agricultural value, because of several environmental and socio-economic constraints, which negatively affect crop productivity and environmental quality, leading to very low farmer income. In such contexts, winter cereal-based cropping systems are prevailing, and soil degradation and the decrease of ecosystem service provision are currently of major concern. Soil erosion, nutrient leaching, reduction of C in soils, certainly represent the main critical issues in these areas. The key concept of the project was to redesign the existing farming systems through the introduction of perennial medicinal and aromatic crops with the conversion from conventional to organic agricultural models. At the same time, new supply chains of organic aromatic plants, with a high added value of final products have been developed, supporting the territorial multifunctional development of the area, through the integration processes between agriculture, processing and other economic activities. This case study will focus on learning from experiences in the project by exploring

the effectiveness of the actions made in terms of soil fertility and health improvement, productivity rising, resilience and landscape valorization. We will investigate the possibility of developing business models aiming at adding value to the agronomic management aimed at soil health conservation with innovative crop products through certification and production standards.

Analysis of social and/or economic barriers

Estimation how DTA for every Barrier/factor will affect variable costs and income for Italian case study shows the following:

- DTA has no influence on variable costs for all three barriers. Only for Initial costs DTA can increase income at the BM Multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas.

Table 10: DTA analysis of social and/or economic barriers trough variable costs and income

Barriers/factors	Influence on variable costs			Influence on income		
	Decrease	No impact	Increase	Decrease	No impact	Increase
Initial costs		X				x
Biodiversity preservation		X			X	
Climate change		x			x	

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver Environmental care ecosystem service

In the context of the Italian case study, business model "Multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection of Environmental care (ecosystem service) sustainable crop production shows varied strengths.

DST and DTA have equal importance for the BM for improving use of resource (40.0%), natural resources protection (42.9%), improve rural livelihoods (33.3%), resilience of ecosystems (40.0%) and governance mechanisms (40.0%) DHK is not preferred in connection within this ecosystem service. The final results reflect DST and DTA as the most effective (40.4%), followed by DHK (19.2%).

DST and DTA have for business model " Multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas " equal essential for Environmental care. DHK is not preferable for Environmental care.

Figure 12. Result of the assessment of DT's according "Environmental care" criteria

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver To preserve landscapes and biodiversity ecosystem service

In the context of the Italian case study, business model "Multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection To preserve landscapes and biodiversity (ecosystem service) sustainable crop production shows varied strengths.

DST and DTA have equal importance for the BM for improving use of resource (40.0%), natural resources protection (40.0%), improve rural livelihoods (33.3%), resilience of ecosystems (42.9%) and governance mechanisms (40.0%) DHK is not preferred in connection within this ecosystem service. The final results reflect DST and DTA as the most effective (41.0%), followed by DHK (18.0%).

DST and DTA have for business model " Multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas " equal essential to preserve landscapes and biodiversity. DHK is not preferable to preserve landscapes and biodiversity.

Figure 13. Result of the assessment of DT's according "To preserve landscapes and biodiversity" criteria

Analysis of delivery of various ecosystem services which depends on a full set of functions defining social preferences and confluence of different pressures.

In the context of the Italian case study, business model "Multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection sustainable crop production shows similar influence of the three digital tools—DHK, DTA, and DST.

The DHK is considered as a most effective tool for the following pressures: Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion, Water scarcity and pollution, Loss of living resources and biodiversity and Climate change.

DST is rated highest in understanding the complexities Land scarcity, degradation and Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns.

Meanwhile, DTA is not preferable for overcoming the pressures.

DHK is preferable for four pressures at the Italian case, business model "Multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas". DST is important to overcome the Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition and Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns. DTA is not preferred for overcoming the pressures.

Table 11: Ranking the DT's according to different pressures

Pressures	Hub of knowledge	Digital tool for analysis	Decision support tool
Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition	1	2	3
Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns	1	2	3
Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion	3	1	2
Water scarcity and pollution	3	1	2
Loss of living resources and biodiversity	3	1	2
Climate change	3	1	2
Stagnation in agricultural research	1	2	3

3.2.5 Italian case study 2

Business model name: Conventional and organic agriculture

Business model type: Agricultural production

The case study focuses on a series of long-term experiments (LTEs) carried out at large plots/field scale at the Centre for Agrienvironmental Research "Enrico Avanzi" of the University of Pisa. Two field experiments are focusing on the application of conservation agriculture techniques (i.e. reduced or no tillage, cover crops), whereas the third one dealt with organic vs conventional farming systems. The oldest field experiment started in 1986 and is comparing on around 2 ha continuous no-till vs annual moldboard ploughing 30 cm depth on durum wheat and pigeon bean crops. Effects on soil fertility (SOC, C stock, bulk density, total N, available P, pH) are regularly assessed at different depths (0–10, 10–30, 30–60 cm), besides with crop yield and nutrient uptake. The second LTE is comparing on 4 ha since 1993 the combination of 2 tillage levels (reduced tillage vs annual ploughing 30 cm depth), 4 N fertilization levels and 4 cover crop species (control, hairy vetch, radish, a mixture of the two) on a 4-year arable crop rotation including durum wheat, sunflower and grain sorghum. Soil fertility issues, crop yield, weed abundance and composition are regularly assessed. In the third LTE, being carried out on 23 ha since 2001, an organic and a conventional management system are being compared on a 4-year (conventional system: durum wheat–chickpea–common wheat and grain sorghum) or 8-year (organic system: common wheat–grain millet–grain sorghum–chickpea–hemmer wheat–alfalfa) arable crop rotation. Soil fertility, crop yield and rheological quality, weed abundance and composition, energy use efficiency, economic balance, are regularly assessed, thanks to the standard field plot size.

Analysis of social and/or economic barriers

Estimation how DTA BM “Conventional and organic agriculture” for every Barrier/factor will affect variable costs and income for Italian case study shows the following:

- DTA has decreasing influence on variable costs for four barriers: Long term results in food security, Biodiversity preservation, Regulation of water cycle and Soil quality. For the same barriers DTA increasing influence on income at the BM “Conventional and organic agriculture”.
- DTA has no impact on the barrier long term return.

Table 12: DTA analysis of social and/or economic barriers through variable costs and income

Barriers/factors	Influence on variable costs			Influence on income		
	Decrease	No impact	Increase	Decrease	No impact	Increase
Long term return		X			X	
Long term results in food security	X					X
Biodiversity preservation	X					X
Regulation of water cycle	X					X
Soil quality	X					X

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver Environmental care ecosystem service

In the context of the Italian case study, business model “Conventional and organic agriculture”, the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection of Environmental care (ecosystem service) sustainable crop production shows varied strengths.

DST and DTA have equal importance for the BM for improving use of resource (40.0%), natural resources protection (40.0%), improve rural livelihoods (40.0%), resilience of ecosystems (40.0%) and governance mechanisms (46.2%) DHK is not preferred in connection within this ecosystem service. The results reflect DST and DTA as the most effective (40.4%), followed by DHK (19.1%).

DST and DTA have for business model “Conventional and organic agriculture” equal essential for Environmental care. DHK is not preferable for Environmental care.

Figure 14. Result of the assessment of DT's according "Environmental care" criteria

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver To protect food and health quality ecosystem service

In the context of the Italian case study, business model "Conventional and organic agriculture", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection of food protection and health quality ecosystem (ecosystem service) sustainable crop production shows varied strengths.

DST and DTA have equal importance for the BM for improving use of resource (40.0%), natural resources protection (40.0%), improve rural livelihoods (40.0%), resilience of ecosystems (40.0%) and governance mechanisms (46.2%) DHK is not preferred in connection within this ecosystem service. The results reflect DST and DTA as the most effective (41.3%), followed by DHK (17.3%).

DST and DTA have for business model "Conventional and organic agriculture" equal essential for Environmental care. DHK is not preferable for Environmental care.

Figure 15. Result of the assessment of DT's according "protect food and health quality" criteria

Analysis of delivery of various ecosystem services which depends on a full set of functions defining social preferences and confluence of different pressures.

In the context of the Italian case study, business model "Conventional and organic agriculture", the application of different tools for supporting soil health within connection sustainable crop production shows similar influence of the three digital tools—DHK, DTA, and DST.

The DHK is considered as a most effective tool for the following pressures: Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion, Water scarcity and pollution, Loss of living resources and biodiversity and Climate change.

DST is rated highest in understanding the complexities of Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition and Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns.

Meanwhile, DTA is not preferable for overcoming the pressures.

DHK is preferable for four pressures at the Italian case, business model "Conventional and organic agriculture". DST is important to overcome the Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition and Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns. DTA is not preferred for overcoming the pressures.

Table 13: Ranking the DT's according different pressures

Pressures	Hub of knowledge	Digital tool for analysis	Decision support tool
Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition	1	2	3
Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns	1	2	3
Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion	3	1	2
Water scarcity and pollution	3	1	2
Loss of living resources and biodiversity	3	1	2
Climate change	3	1	2
Stagnation in agricultural research	1	2	3

3.2.6 Italy case study 3

Business model name: District of the Sands

Business model type: Collective and value chain

The coastal area of the Emilia-Romagna Region is an area with a strong agricultural vocation with high-quality horticultural production. However, soil health faces strong pressures due to the high share of sand components and salinisation, subsidence and loss of organic matter and contamination. Therefore, the project will investigate the possibility to introduce carbon farming that can enhance organic matter. Due to the substantial extent of diffusion sandy soil in the area (six municipalities involved), we will investigate the possibility to develop a Biodistrict to develop new business models aiming at adding value to the soil conservation management with food production through certification and production standards.

Analysis of social and/or economic barriers

Estimation of how DTA influences variable costs and income for the Italy case study shows the following:

- **Sustainable crop production** is associated with increased variable costs and increased income, indicating that while adapting practices may require more inputs or technology, they lead to greater profitability.
- **Long-term results in food security** also increase variable costs and no impact on income.
- **Biodiversity preservation** is beneficial both in terms of reduced costs and increased income.
- **Climate change** mitigation through DTA is seen to increase variable costs and decrease income.

- **Regulation of the water cycle** brings increased costs and increased income, reflecting the importance of water-efficient practices in sandy areas.
- **Soil quality** improvements increase the costs cost and have no impact on income.

Table 14: DTA analysis of social and/or economic barriers through variable costs and income

Barriers/factors	Influence on variable costs			Influence on income		
	Decrease	No impact	Increase	Decrease	No impact	Increase
Sustainable crop production			X			X
Long term results in food security			X		X	
Biodiversity preservation			X			X
Climate change			X	X		
Regulation of water cycle			X			X
Soil quality			X		X	

Analysis of delivery of various ecosystem services which depends on a full set of functions defining social preferences and confluence of different pressures.

In the case study, assessing the response of the three NOVASOIL tools—DHK, DTA, and DST—to major pressures on soil health reveals distinct strengths for each.

The DHK is ranked as the most effective tool in addressing poverty, hunger, malnutrition, inadequate diets and consumption patterns, climate change, and stagnation in agricultural research. This highlights its strong role in community empowerment, education, and awareness, which are foundational for shifting long-term behaviors and addressing systemic socio-economic drivers of soil degradation.

The DTA performs best in tackling loss of biodiversity, providing precise data and analytics to support conservation strategies and guide targeted

ecological interventions. It is also consistently ranked second across most other categories, showing its strength as a supportive analytical tool that enables evidence-based planning and monitoring.

The DST emerges as the most effective for land degradation and water scarcity and pollution, reflecting its practical utility in resource planning, optimization of land use, and infrastructure-based decision-making. These tools support on-the-ground action for mitigating environmental degradation in real time.

DHK plays a key role in addressing social, behavioral, and knowledge-based pressures. The DTA is essential for ecological monitoring and understanding systemic issues like biodiversity loss. DST excels in operational and resource-focused challenges such as land degradation and water management. A combined, strategic use of all three tools is critical for effective and holistic soil health management.

Table 15: Ranking the DT's according to different pressures

Pressures	Hub of knowledge	Digital tool for analysis	Decision support tool
Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition	1	2	3
Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns	1	2	3
Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion	3	2	1
Water scarcity and pollution	3	2	1
Loss of living resources and biodiversity	3	1	2
Climate change	1	2	3
Stagnation in agricultural research	1	2	3

3.2.7 Latvia case study 1

Business model name: Crop production and animal farming

Business model type: Value chain

Agriculture crop (winter wheat, barley, rapeseed oil, legumes) production and animal husbandry requires smart farming technologies to follow the environmental measures defined by the Green Deal and the Farm to Fork

strategy to ensure sustainable farming practices by effective soil management, with an increase in soil fertility, organic matter, and nutrient cycle management investigated through the project activities and business models.

Analysis of social and/or economic barriers

Estimation of how DTA influences variable costs and income for the Latvia case study shows the following:

- **Initial costs** are perceived as a factor that decreases variable costs but also reduces income, indicating a short-term financial barrier despite cost-saving potential, possibly due to lower returns during early adoption phases.
- **Food demand** increases variable costs and income, reflecting the higher production inputs needed to meet market demand, which are offset by improved revenue.
- **Long-term results in food security** are seen as having no impact on variable costs but a negative impact on income, suggesting that benefits may not translate into immediate financial gains.
- **Biodiversity preservation** reduces variable costs and increases income, highlighting ecological and economic synergy.
- **Climate change** is similarly addressed positively, with reduced variable costs and increased income, implying DTA supports climate-resilient practices that are economically favorable.
- **Regulation of the water cycle** has no effect on costs and income.
- **Soil quality** improvements come at the cost of increased variable costs but has no impact on income.

Table 16: DTA analysis of social and/or economic barriers through variable costs and income

Barriers/factors	Influence on variable costs			Influence on income		
	Decrease	No impact	Increase	Decrease	No impact	Increase
Initial costs	X			X		
Food demand		X				X
Long term results in food security		X			X	
Biodiversity preservation	X					X
Climate change	X					X
Regulation of water cycle		X			X	

Soil quality			x		X	
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Place "x" on every row once for variable costs and once for income.

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver Environmental care ecosystem service

In the context of the Crop Production and Animal Farming business model, the use of the three NOVASOIL toolbox tools is evaluated for their support of CAP objectives related to environmental care and the delivery of key ecosystem services such as air quality, soil quality, and water quality.

For Use of Resources, DST demonstrates the highest effectiveness (65.7%), indicating its strength in optimizing input use and improving resource efficiency in agricultural practices.

In Natural Resources Protection, the DST again stands out (75.0%), showing its significant role in safeguarding soil, water, and air quality through scenario-based planning and targeted interventions.

For Improving Rural Livelihoods, the DHK leads (62.3%), emphasizing the importance of shared learning, education, and knowledge transfer for sustainable rural development.

In terms of Resilience of Ecosystems, the DTA scores highest (45.8%), reflecting its capacity to model and support ecological adaptation and system stability.

Regarding Governance Mechanisms, the DHK is most effective (63.3%), highlighting its contribution to policy understanding and compliance.

In the Final Result, the DST achieves the strongest overall impact (45.39%), positioning it as the most valuable tool for integrating environmental, agronomic, and decision-making goals.

This distribution indicates that DST are essential for operational and environmental outcomes, while the DHK excels in social dimensions like governance and community livelihoods. DTA are most effective in ecological modeling and resilience, but their overall contribution is more targeted. As in previous assessments, no single tool covers all areas fully demonstrating the need for integrated deployment across knowledge-sharing, analytical, and decision-support functionalities.

Figure 16. Result of the assessment of DT's according "Environmental care" criteria

Assessing the toolbox tools to delivery of CAP goal - To preserve landscapes and biodiversity CAP and landscape and scenery and biodiversity ecosystem services

This assessment explores the effectiveness of the NOVASOIL toolbox tools in supporting biodiversity protection and landscape preservation within the context of sustainable agriculture.

For Use of Resources, both the DHK and DTA share the highest effectiveness (44.4%), highlighting their value in promoting efficient, biodiversity-friendly resource use practices.

In Natural Resources Protection, the DHK leads decisively (63.9%), showing its strength in supporting knowledge-based approaches to protecting soil, habitats, and ecological balance.

For Improving Rural Livelihoods, the DHK again ranks highest (53.9%), emphasizing the importance of education and community engagement in preserving cultural landscapes and biodiversity-related economic opportunities.

When assessing Resilience of Ecosystems, both the DHK and DTA are equally effective (45.5%), reflecting their joint potential in supporting ecosystem stability and landscape functionality.

Regarding Governance Mechanisms, the DST dominates (67.5%), showing it is the most effective tool for planning, compliance, and integration of biodiversity-focused policies into land management.

In the Result, the DHK shows the highest overall impact (51.93%), demonstrating that knowledge-sharing, awareness, and stakeholder involvement are central to preserving landscapes and biodiversity.

DHK emerges as the most effective tool in this assessment, especially in areas connected to biodiversity awareness, ecological knowledge, and community resilience. DST are essential for governance and structured planning, while DTA play a supportive role, particularly in ecosystem monitoring.

Figure 17. Result of the assessment of DT's according "To preserve landscapes and biodiversity" criteria

Analysis of delivery of various ecosystem services which depends on a full set of functions defining social preferences and confluence of different pressures.

In Latvian case study, BM "Crop production and animal farming" the application of the three NOVASOIL tools—DHK, DTA, and DST—demonstrates differentiated effectiveness in tackling a range of pressures impacting soil health and sustainability.

The DTA is rated as the most effective in addressing poverty and malnutrition, climate change, and water scarcity and pollution, highlighting its strong

capacity for data-driven insights and targeted analysis. These tools support the diagnosis of complex environmental and socio-economic issues, enabling precise responses to challenges like water quality, changing weather patterns, and food insecurity.

The DST emerges as the best solution for land degradation and unsustainable consumption, underscoring its importance in resource planning, land use optimization, and tactical decision-making to mitigate soil exhaustion and improve sustainability outcomes in food systems.

The DHK is ranked highest in tackling biodiversity loss and stagnation in agricultural research, reflecting its critical role in raising awareness, fostering collaboration, and building capacity among stakeholders. It is especially effective when addressing pressures that require behavioral change, knowledge transfer, or stakeholder engagement.

The DTA excels in quantifying and responding to environmental and social pressures through analytics. The DST provides strategic solutions for operational land and resource issues, while the DHK is essential for systemic learning and innovation. Their complementary use is crucial for building a soil health strategy that is both scientifically grounded and socially responsive.

Table 17: Ranking the DT's according different pressures

Pressures	Hub of knowledge	Digital tool for analysis	Decision support tool
Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition	3	1	2
Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns	3	2	1
Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion	2	3	1
Water scarcity and pollution	2	1	3
Loss of living resources and biodiversity	1	3	2
Climate change	3	1	2
Stagnation in agricultural research	1	2	3

3.2.8 Latvia case study 2

Business model name: The forest management

Business model type: Forestry soils

The forest management BM demonstration plots of the Pasaules dabas fonds (associate partner of WWF Latvia) have different owners, but their views on the forest are similar. Here, forest owners work for the benefit of the present values while retaining the ability to exploit the vast forest values of tomorrow.

The demonstration areas differ in size, forest stand and natural conditions. Through contractual agreements (cooperation) with forest owners on a voluntary basis, seminars and internships are organized for other forest owners, students, etc. to maintain the forest and not to cut down all trees, to manage the forest in an environmentally friendly way and also to achieve economic benefits. There are about 5-10 events per year with a total number of 200-300 participants.

Analysis of social and/or economic barriers

Estimation of how DTA influences variable costs and income for the Latvia forest management case study shows the following:

- **Long-term return** is associated with a *decrease in variable costs* and an *no impact in income*, indicating that DTA may provide strategic benefits that reduce operational expenses.
- **Sustainable crop production** has *no impact on variable costs* but is linked to an *increase in income*, suggesting that DTA may enhance profitability through improved practices without significantly altering cost structures.
- **Food demand** also shows *no impact on variable costs* and an *increase in income*, reflecting that DTA may help forest managers or landowners respond to market opportunities and boost revenues without increasing input requirements.
- **Climate change** is associated with an *increase in variable costs* with no impact *in income*, indicating a potential barrier.
- **Regulation of the water cycle** has *no impact on costs and income*.
- **Soil quality** improvements are associated with an *increase in variable costs* and an *increase in income*, meaning that while DTA implementation may require higher investment in forest soil maintenance, it can lead to higher returns over time.

Table 18: DTA analysis of social and/or economic barriers through variable costs and income

Barriers/factors	Influence on variable costs			Influence on income		
	Decrease	No impact	Increase	Decrease	No impact	Increase
Long term return	x				x	
Sustainable crop production		x				x
Food demand		x				x
Climate change			x		x	
Regulation of water cycle		x			x	

Soil quality			x			x
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Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver Environmental care ecosystem service

This assessment evaluates the effectiveness of the NOVASOIL toolbox tools in promoting environmental care and improving Air quality, Soil quality, and Water quality ecosystem services in agriculture.

For Use of Resources, both the DHK and DTA are equally the most effective tools (45.5%), emphasizing their role in promoting efficient and sustainable use of agricultural inputs that impact soil and water quality.

In Natural Resources Protection, DHK leads with a substantial margin (68.8%), indicating its key role in spreading knowledge and practices essential for safeguarding air, soil, and water ecosystems.

For Improving Rural Livelihoods, both the DHK and the DST are equally impactful (42.9%), showing how education and decision support together enhance environmental awareness and economic resilience in rural areas.

When it comes to Resilience of Ecosystems, the DHK is again the top performer (44.0%), highlighting its role in supporting the adaptive capacity of farming systems to protect ecosystem functions.

In terms of Governance Mechanisms, both the DTA and DST share the highest influence (46.2%), reinforcing their importance in supporting compliance, policy implementation, and structured environmental planning.

In the Final Result, the DHK scores the highest overall (49.91%), demonstrating that access to knowledge and awareness-building are fundamental to advancing environmental care in agriculture.

The DHK is the strongest overall performer, especially for natural resources protection, ecosystem resilience, and community engagement. The DST complements this with strengths in livelihoods and governance, while the DTA proves valuable in resource use and governance planning.

Figure 18. Result of the assessment of DT's according "Environmental care" criteria

Analysis of delivery of various ecosystem services which depends on a full set of functions defining social preferences and confluence of different pressures.

In Latvian case study, BM "The forest management" The DHK is rated most effective in four categories: poverty and malnutrition, inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption, biodiversity loss, and stagnation in agricultural research. This underscores its key role in education, awareness-raising, and stakeholder engagement. It is especially suited for pressures requiring knowledge dissemination, community involvement, and institutional learning.

The DTA performs best in land scarcity and degradation, highlighting its capacity to quantify soil conditions, monitor degradation trends, and provide evidence for targeted intervention. It also consistently ranks second across several other categories, reinforcing its value as a supportive analytical tool in both ecological and socio-economic domains.

The DST stands out in managing water scarcity and pollution and climate change, indicating its strength in technical planning, adaptive management, and scenario simulation. It is ideal for addressing complex, system-level challenges that require real-time decision-making and strategic action.

The DHK leads in addressing social and institutional barriers to soil health, such as poverty, behavior, and knowledge gaps. The DTA provides robust

support for land and biodiversity-related pressures, while the DST is most effective in tackling environmental and infrastructural challenges.

Table 19: Ranking the DT's according to different pressures

Pressures	Hub of knowledge	Digital tool for analysis	Decision support tool
Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition	1	3	2
Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns	1	2	3
Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion	2	1	3
Water scarcity and pollution	2	3	1
Loss of living resources and biodiversity	1	3	2
Climate change	3	2	1
Stagnation in agricultural research	1	2	3

3.2.9 Spain case study 1

Business model name: Integrated production

Business model type: Value chain

With the integrated production program, sustainable agriculture in Andalusia has been promoted. The statistics offered by the regional government show that participation in this measure has been increasing over the past few years. Specifically, in the olive grove sector, there is a lot of competition. Recent research works highlighted the increase of soil organic carbon due to crop/land management.

Analysis of social and/or economic barriers

Estimation of how DTA influences variable costs and income for the Spain case study shows the following:

- **Long-term return** is associated with an *increase in variable costs* and an *increase in income*, suggesting that DTA implementation requires higher investment but offers significant long-term financial benefits.
- **Sustainable crop production** leads to a *decrease in variable costs* and an *increase in income*, indicating that DTA supports efficient and profitable practices aligned with integrated production systems.
- **Food demand** has *no impact on variable costs* but results in an *increase in income*, meaning DTA enables producers to meet demand more effectively without increasing operational inputs.
- **Long-term results in food security** result in a *decrease in variable costs* and an *increase in income*, highlighting that DTA contributes to

efficient practices that ensure food security and economic viability over time.

- **Biodiversity preservation** is linked to an *increase in variable costs* and no impact *in income*, possibly due to the added costs of ecological practices that don't immediately translate into financial gain.
- **Climate change** is associated with a *decrease in variable costs* and an *increase in income*, showing DTA's potential to promote resilience and adaptive strategies that are both cost-effective and economically rewarding.
- **Regulation of the water cycle** also leads to a *decrease in variable costs* and an *increase in income*, reflecting the value of DTA in enhancing water efficiency and supporting productivity.
- **Soil quality** improvements result in a *decrease in variable costs* and an *increase in income*, underlining DTA's effectiveness in boosting soil health while improving financial outcomes.

Table 20: DTA analysis of social and/or economic barriers through variable costs and income

Barriers/factors	Influence on variable costs			Influence on income		
	Decrease	No impact	Increase	Decrease	No impact	Increase
Long term return			X			X
Sustainable crop production	X					X
Food demand		X				X
Long term results in food security	X					X
Biodiversity preservation			X		X	
Climate change	X					X
Regulation of water cycle	X					X
Soil quality	X					X

Assessing of the Toolbox Tools to Deliver the CAP Goal “Climate Change” and Ecosystem Services – Climate Regulation and Carbon Storage

This assessment explores how each of the NOVASOIL toolbox tools contributes to climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture, focusing on tools that support carbon storage and environmental resilience.

For Use of Resources, DST is the most effective (56.8%), reflecting its strength in optimizing resource usage.

In Natural Resources Protection, the DST again leads (53.2%), showing its role in protecting soil and organic matter critical for carbon retention and climate resilience.

Regarding Improving Rural Livelihoods, DST shows the highest influence (60.8%), suggesting that climate-smart practices supported by DTA can improve economic stability in rural areas.

In Resilience of Ecosystems, the DST performs strongest (56.0%), confirming its value in adapting agricultural systems to climate risks and enhancing ecosystem functionality.

For Governance Mechanisms, the DHK is the top performer (69.0%), indicating the importance of education, information dissemination, and stakeholder engagement in climate-related policy and land-use planning.

In the Final Result, the DST shows the highest overall impact (53.89%), making it the most effective tool for addressing climate change objectives and carbon-related ecosystem services in agriculture.

DST emerges as the leading instrument for tackling climate change, excelling in resource management, ecosystem resilience, and rural adaptation. DHK complements this by supporting governance and awareness efforts.

Figure 19. Result of the assessment of DT's according "Climate Change" criteria

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver Environmental care ecosystem service

This evaluation highlights how each of the NOVASOIL toolbox tools contributes to achieving environmental care objectives and improving key ecosystem services in agricultural systems.

For Use of Resources, DST is the most effective (56.8%), supporting optimized and climate-smart input usage that minimizes environmental pollution and enhances air and soil quality.

In Natural Resources Protection, DST clearly leads (70.2%), emphasizing its strong contribution to conserving soil health, water resources, and atmospheric quality.

When it comes to Improving Rural Livelihoods, the DST again takes the lead (68.1%), showing that environmentally conscious practices supported by DTA can also yield meaningful economic benefits.

In Resilience of Ecosystems, the DST performs strongest (60.8%), reinforcing its value in helping ecosystems recover and adapt.

Regarding Governance Mechanisms, the DHK is the top performer (63.3%), highlighting its crucial role in fostering awareness, training, and policy understanding necessary for sound environmental governance.

For the Final Result, the DST achieves the highest overall score (60.9%), confirming it as the most impactful tool in supporting environmental care and related ecosystem service goals.

DST is the dominant performer in this context, leading in five out of six categories, particularly in operational effectiveness and environmental impact. DHK remains essential in governance-related aspects, showing that education and policy support are also vital components of a sustainable environmental strategy.

Figure 20. Result of the assessment of DT's according "Environmental care" criteria

Assessing the toolbox tools to deliver of CAP goal - To preserve landscapes and biodiversity CAP and landscape and scenery and biodiversity ecosystem services

This assessment evaluates the role of NOVASOIL toolbox tools in supporting biodiversity conservation and landscape protection within sustainable farming systems.

For Use of Resources, the DTA is the most effective (63.3%), indicating its strong potential in promoting resource-efficient practices that contribute to landscape preservation and biodiversity integrity.

In Natural Resources Protection, the DST leads (58.1%), showing its strength in managing soil, water, and habitat resources that underpin ecological diversity.

When it comes to Improving Rural Livelihoods, the DST performs best (51.2%), reflecting its contribution to integrating biodiversity-friendly practices with economic opportunities for local communities.

For Resilience of Ecosystems, the DST is the top performer (65.1%), supporting adaptive and diverse land systems that maintain long-term ecological balance.

Regarding Governance Mechanisms, the DHK has the highest impact (72.3%), underscoring the value of education, knowledge sharing, and awareness-building in ensuring participatory biodiversity and landscape management.

In the Final Result, the DST ranks highest overall (54.33%), making it the most effective tool for addressing CAP biodiversity goals and related ecosystem services.

The DST shows dominant performance across most categories, especially in biodiversity protection, ecosystem resilience, and livelihoods. The DHK plays a critical role in governance and stakeholder engagement, while the DTA contributes significantly to resource-use optimization.

Figure 21. Result of the assessment of DT's according "To preserve landscapes and biodiversity" criteria

Analysis of delivery of various ecosystem services which depends on a full set of functions defining social preferences and confluence of different pressures.

DHK shows the lowest overall effectiveness among the three tools in this assessment. It ranks second in only two cases—inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns, and stagnation in agricultural research. In the remaining five categories, it is ranked third.

The DTA demonstrates strong performance in addressing ecological pressures. It is ranked first in two critical categories: degradation and water scarcity/pollution. In most other categories, it is consistently ranked second, showing a solid, supportive role.

The DST is the clear leader in this assessment. It ranks first in five out of the seven pressures examined: poverty and malnutrition, inadequate diets, biodiversity loss, climate change, and stagnation in agricultural research. In the remaining two areas - land degradation and water management, it ranks second. This makes the most versatile and action-oriented tool. Its strength lies in strategic and operational planning, providing practical support for tackling complex and systemic challenges related to soil health and agricultural sustainability.

The NOVASOIL tools have complementary roles. DST is the most effective for implementation and decision-making. The DTA offers essential data and insight, particularly for environmental pressures. DHK supports long-term transformation through awareness, training, and community engagement.

Table 21: Ranking the DT's according different pressures

Pressures	Hub of knowledge	Digital tool for analysis	Decision support tool
Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition	3	2	1
Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns	2	3	1
Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion	3	1	2
Water scarcity and pollution	3	1	2
Loss of living resources and biodiversity	3	2	1
Climate change	3	2	1
Stagnation in agricultural research	2	3	1

3.2.10 Spain case study 2

Business model name: Organic wine in Rueda, Spain (Rueda)

Business model type: Value chain

It is a value-chain related contract solution, where only grapes produced ecologically are bought by the winery Herederos del Marqués de Riscal, S.A (from now on, Riscal), to produce two selected varieties: MARQUÉS DE RISCAL ORGANIC and MARQUÉS DE RISCAL SAUVIGNON BLANC ORGANIC. In the Rueda case study, grape producers are not associated, however, they are integrated into the value chain by complying to the winery standards and have periodic controls on quality and residues, and have a strict protocol of organic production of high standards.

Analysis of social and/or economic barriers

Estimation of how DTA influences variable costs and income for the Rueda organic wine case study shows the following:

- **Initial costs** are reduced by DTA, while income is increased, indicating that DTA helps lower the financial barrier to adopting organic production while improving profitability through market integration.
- **Long-term return** is associated with an *increase in variable costs* and an *increase in income*, suggesting that DTA supports long-term strategies that may require investment but provide strong financial outcomes over time.
- **Sustainable crop production** leads to *increased variable costs* and *increased income*.
- **Long-term results in food security** show *no impact* on both costs and income.
- **Climate change** adaptation is linked to *increased variable costs* and *increased income*, suggesting that climate-resilient practices supported by DTA involve investment but lead to greater stability and returns.
- **Regulation of the water cycle** is also associated with *increased variable costs* and *increased income*, highlighting that DTA contributes to more sustainable water use.
- **Soil quality** improvements result in *increased variable costs* and *increased income*.

Table 22: DTA analysis of social and/or economic barriers through variable costs and income

Barriers/factors	Influence on variable costs			Influence on income		
	Decrease	No impact	Increase	Decrease	No impact	Increase
Initial costs	DTA decreases initial costs					DTA increases income

Long term return			DTA increases long term return			DTA increases long term results
Sustainable crop production			DTA increases sustainable crop production			DTA increases sustainable crop production
Long term results in food security		DTA has no impact in the long-term food security			DTA has no impact in the long-term food security	
Climate change			DTA increases adaptation to climate change			DTA increases adaptation to climate change
Regulation of water cycle			DTA increases regulation of the water cycle			DTA increases regulation of the water cycle
Soil quality			DTA increases soil quality			DTA increases soil quality

Assessing of the toolbox tools to deliver Environmental care ecosystem service

This assessment examines the contributions of the NOVASOIL toolbox tools to environmental care and related ecosystem services in agriculture.

For Use of Resources, both the DTA and DST are equally the most effective (47.1%), showing their value in optimizing input use to reduce environmental impact on air, water, and soil.

In Natural Resources Protection, the DTA and DST again share the highest score (47.1%), indicating their usefulness in managing and conserving environmental assets essential for ecosystem services.

Regarding Improving Rural Livelihoods, both tools maintain equal top effectiveness (47.1%), highlighting how environmentally sustainable practices can also support income generation and community well-being.

For Resilience of Ecosystems, the DTA and DST are once more tied (47.1%), demonstrating their strength in promoting systems that adapt to and recover from environmental stressors.

In the area of Governance Mechanisms, the DST leads clearly (66.4%), reinforcing its essential role in supporting policy implementation, regulatory compliance, and structured planning for environmental goals.

For the Final Result, the DST achieves the highest overall score (52.21%), confirming its status as the most effective and versatile tool for advancing environmental care and enhancing ecosystem services.

The DST consistently shows high impact, especially in governance and overall effectiveness. While the DTA matches its performance in many environmental categories, the DST emerges as the most comprehensive solution.

Figure 22. Result of the assessment of DT's according "Environmental care" criteria

Assessing of the toolbox tools to delivery of CAP goal Protecting food and health quality and the quality and security products, and farm animal health and welfare ecosystem services.

This assessment evaluates how the NOVASOIL toolbox tools contribute to food safety, health standards, and the sustainability of animal production systems.

For Use of Resources, DST is the most effective (62.8%), indicating its capacity to guide efficient, health-conscious input use in both crop and livestock systems.

In Natural Resources Protection, DST also leads (62.8%), reinforcing its role in maintaining the environmental conditions necessary for healthy food and animal systems.

Regarding Improving Rural Livelihoods, the DST ranks highest (57.5%), showing that aligning health and quality standards with production benefits farmers economically.

For Resilience of Ecosystems, the DST performs best (62.8%), supporting resilient, high-quality production systems that ensure long-term food and animal welfare security.

In terms of Governance Mechanisms, both the DTA and the DST are equally effective (46.2%), highlighting their importance in monitoring, compliance, and certification related to food quality and animal welfare.

For the Final Result, the DST once again achieves the highest score (57.19%), confirming its comprehensive contribution to food and health quality goals.

The DST is the dominant performer across all key areas, making it the most impactful tool for promoting food safety, product quality, and animal welfare. Its decision-oriented functionalities help align on-farm practices with high standards for both human and animal health. The DTA complements this in governance-related aspects.

Figure 23. Result of the assessment of DT's according "Protecting food and health quality" criteria

Analysis of delivery of various ecosystem services which depends on a full set of functions defining social preferences and confluence of different pressures.

The DHK is ranked first in only two categories: climate change and stagnation in agricultural research. This highlights its value in long-term processes that require education, capacity building, and knowledge transfer—areas where behavior change, innovation, and shared learning are essential. However, in five out of seven pressures, DHK ranks third, suggesting that while it is critical for institutional and cultural transformation, it is less effective in addressing urgent or technical issues such as land degradation or water scarcity.

The DTA is ranked first in two categories: water scarcity and pollution and loss of biodiversity. These results reflect its strength in environmental monitoring, diagnostics, and data-driven insight, especially in areas where precision and ecological understanding are needed. It also ranks second in two other categories, confirming its stable role across most pressures. However, it scores third in three categories, indicating it is not always the primary tool when strategic planning or social intervention is needed.

The DST shows the strongest overall performance, being ranked first in three categories: poverty and malnutrition, inadequate diets, and land degradation. It consistently ranks second in the remaining four areas. This underscores its role as the most balanced and action-oriented tool, capable of supporting both social and environmental challenges through strategic decision-making, planning, and implementation. DHK is particularly effective where practical solutions and operational choices are critical.

Each NOVASOIL tool plays a complementary role. The DST is the leading performer, providing practical and strategic value across most soil health pressures. The DTA is essential for ecological understanding and environmental assessment. The DHK contributes most in areas that require systemic change through learning and innovation.

Table 23: Ranking the DT's according to different pressures

Pressures	Hub of knowledge	Digital tool for analysis	Decision support tool
Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition	3	2	1
Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns	2	3	1
Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion	3	2	1
Water scarcity and pollution	3	1	2
Loss of living resources and biodiversity	3	1	2
Climate change	1	3	2
Stagnation in agricultural research	1	3	2

3.1 Integrated Analysis of Digital Tools by business model types

3.1.1 Business model type: Value chain

Analysis of the usefulness of DTA in relation to social and economic barriers

The implementation of Digital Tool 2 (DTA) across Bulgaria, Latvia, and Spain reveals a consistent pattern of transformation in Value chain business model. While each country presents context-specific nuances, a common trajectory

can be observed in how DTA influences operational cost structures, income dynamics, and long-term sustainability.

Initial investment is widely perceived as a significant short-term barrier. In Bulgaria and Latvia, it is viewed as a cost-increasing factor with the potential to reduce income during early adoption. However, in some cases such as in Spain, DTA also contributes to mitigating this financial hurdle.

The effect of DTA on variable costs varies across countries and specific goals. In certain contexts, such as biodiversity preservation or climate adaptation, its implementation may lead to increased variable costs due to the adoption of more complex or ecologically sensitive practices. Conversely, in areas like water cycle regulation, sustainable crop production, and soil quality improvements, DTA often leads to a reduction in variable costs. This is especially prominent in Spain, where its efficiency-enhancing capabilities are more extensively utilized.

Across all countries, the use of DTA is consistently associated with increased income, particularly when focused on soil health, climate-resilient practices, and sustainable production systems. In Bulgaria and Spain, improved soil quality translates directly into higher revenues. DTA also enables producers to respond more effectively to food demand without a proportional increase in input, which strengthens profitability.

Not all benefits result in immediate financial gain. In Latvia, long-term outcomes related to food security are often perceived as neutral or even negative in terms of short-term income. Soil quality improvements consistently emerge as a point of convergence, where DTA not only supports agronomic performance but also yields clear financial benefits, especially in Spain. Climate adaptation practices, supported by the tool, promote economic resilience and operational stability. Similarly, water management efficiency is notably improved through DTA, particularly in regions facing scarcity (Spain), which enhances both productivity and profitability.

Biodiversity-friendly practices, while not always linked to short-term income gains, position producers advantageously in light of evolving regulatory and consumer expectations. These practices align with broader sustainability goals, adding reputational and strategic value to the business model.

We can conclude that the most substantial value of DTA lies in its long-term strategic contribution. Despite short-term barriers, the tool supports a gradual and transformative shift toward more resilient, data-driven, and profitable agricultural systems. The value chain business model shaped by DTA is centered on sustainable intensification, where producers aim to achieve higher productivity with optimized resource use. This model prioritizes long-term profitability, often requiring upfront investments that yield benefits over time. It enhances producers' responsiveness to market demand. Furthermore, it integrates environmental considerations, including biodiversity, climate adaptation, and soil health, as essential components of the production system.

Analysis of the contribution of the digital tools to the delivery of various ecosystem services

Across Bulgaria, Latvia, and Spain, DST shape a modern value chain business model that integrates ecological, operational, and social dimensions. Despite national variations in priorities and tool effectiveness, a clear and structured model emerges, built upon three core technological pillars: DST, Hubs of Knowledge, and DTA.

In all countries, DST is seen as strategic enablers that optimize resource use, strengthen governance, and enhance resilience. They are not isolated solutions but function most effectively when integrated with knowledge-sharing platforms and data-driven analytical tools.

DST are consistently recognized as the central instrument for driving operational efficiency, governance, and environmental planning. In Spain and Latvia, they dominate most categories including biodiversity, climate resilience, and structured decision-making. In Bulgaria, they are most effective in addressing unsustainable agricultural practices and guiding conservation planning.

Hubs of Knowledge play a pivotal role in governance, awareness, and community livelihoods. Across all contexts, they support stakeholder engagement and long-term capacity building. This is especially emphasized in Bulgaria and Latvia, where they are seen as critical for social cohesion and sustainability culture.

DTA provide targeted impact in areas such as resource monitoring, ecological modeling, and resilience tracking. Though generally rated lower than DST and DHK, they offer essential feedback loops that make strategic and educational tools more responsive and adaptive.

Key similarities that are found across the value chain business models are:

Integrated Use Required: No single tool is sufficient. All three countries emphasize the need for a synergistic combination of DST, DHK, and DTA to address the full spectrum of value chain challenges—from production to ecosystem management and community well-being.

Strategic Planning & Governance: DST are universally linked to improved governance and long-term planning. This suggests their centrality in value chain leadership and risk management.

Multifunctional Landscape Application: Especially in Bulgaria and Spain, the tools are valued for managing complex systems like vineyards and rural tourism, supporting both ecological outcomes and economic livelihoods.

While Bulgaria presents a more balanced perception of all tools (with slightly higher value on Hubs of Knowledge), Spain (both assessments) consistently identifies DST as the dominant force across nearly all impact categories. Latvia places greater emphasis on knowledge and community-oriented tools, viewing Digital Tools more as a supporting feature.

In Spain, climate adaptation, biodiversity protection, and ecosystem resilience are leading concerns. Bulgaria emphasizes soil health, resource conservation,

and sustainable livelihoods. Latvia focuses on governance, biodiversity awareness, and community resilience.

DST are not only technological solutions but act as structural anchors of a modern value chain business model. Their integration with knowledge platforms and analytical technologies supports a holistic transformation of agriculture and land management, addressing environmental, operational, and social demands simultaneously. While national contexts influence the emphasis placed on each tool, the universal recommendation is integration, complementarity, and strategic deployment across all phases of the value chain.

Analysis of the toolbox for delivery of various ecosystem services according to the social preferences

In all countries, the value chain model is structured around:

DST as the core mechanism for planning, governance, and aligning land use with strategic goals. DTA as enablers of data-driven insights, especially for tracking environmental pressures. Hubs of Knowledge as social catalysts that facilitate education, innovation, and stakeholder engagement.

All contexts confirm that ecosystem services require integration of these tools. No single tool is sufficient on its own. Their synergy ensures that ecological goals (e.g., soil restoration, biodiversity) are matched with social value (e.g., livelihoods, education) and economic sustainability.

Spain prioritizes DST for implementation, food safety, and operational impact. Latvia emphasizes Digital Tools for pressure-response analytics and Hubs for system learning. Bulgaria balances all three, highlighting their combined value for vineyard landscapes and rural tourism.

3.1.2 Business model type: Agricultural production/value chain

Analysis of the usefulness of DTA in relation to social and economic barriers

Long term return, Sustainable crop production, Food demand and Biodiversity preservation are barriers for which DT 2 has no influence on variable costs in a CO₂-Land business model. From these four barriers Long term return and Sustainable crop production impose over increasing income. The rest two have no income impact. While DTA impact on Soil quality is decreasing factor for variable costs, it is strongly associated with increased income, highlighting its value as a strategic, long-term benefit. DTA has influence on Climate change as decreasing variable costs and income increasing.

Analysis of the contribution of digital tools to the delivery of various ecosystem services

DST are essential for Climate change guiding use of resources that align with improvement rural livelihoods and resilience of ecosystems. DTA plays a key

role in improvement natural resource protection and governance mechanism. DHK is not preferable for Climate change.

DST for business model "CO2-Land" is essential for Environmental care guiding use of resources that align with natural resources and resilience of ecosystems. DTA plays a key role in improvement rural livelihoods and governance mechanism. DHK is not preferable for Climate change.

DST for business model "CO2-Land" is essential for Environmental care guiding use of resources that align with natural resources and resilience of ecosystems. DTA plays a key role in improvement rural livelihoods and governance mechanism. DHK is not preferable for Climate change.

Analysis of the toolbox for delivery of various ecosystem services according to the social preferences

DHK is preferable for Climate change for the business model "Agricultural production/value chain". DTA is important to overcome the Land scarcity, degradation and soil depletion. The most important tool is DST which is key in following barriers: Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition, Inadequate diets and unsustainable consumption patterns, Water scarcity and pollution, Loss of living resources and biodiversity and Stagnation in agricultural research.

3.1.3 Business model type: Collective and value chain

Analysis of the usefulness of DTA in relation to social and economic barriers

The two Italian case studies — Multifunctional and Sustainable Local Development of Marginal Areas and District of the Sands — highlight differing socio-economic dynamics under the collective and value chain business model. In the first case, the DST does not influence variable costs but can contribute to increased income through initial investments. In contrast, the District of the Sands demonstrates that sustainable crop production raises both variable costs and income, suggesting long-term profitability. However, some measures, such as climate change mitigation, increase costs while reducing income. Other services, like biodiversity preservation and water cycle regulation, tend to improve income despite higher costs, indicating a mixed economic impact depending on the type of service implemented.

Analysis of the contribution of digital tools to the delivery of various ecosystem services

Ecosystem service delivery varies across tools and contexts. In the multifunctional development model, both the DST and the DTA are essential for supporting environmental care and the preservation of landscapes and biodiversity. The DHK, while not preferred for environmental outcomes, is valuable in addressing social pressures, such as poverty, inequality, malnutrition, and unsustainable consumption patterns. In the District of the Sands, the Hub plays a critical role in managing social, behavioral, and

informational challenges, whereas the Digital Tool is more suited for ecological monitoring and addressing systemic environmental issues. The DST, meanwhile, is particularly effective in operational domains such as land degradation and water management.

Analysis of the toolbox for delivery of various ecosystem services according to the social preferences

The analysis of ecosystem service delivery, which considers the full range of social preferences and the interaction of multiple pressures, reveals differing strengths among the tools. In the case of the Multifunctional and Sustainable Local Development of Marginal Areas, the DHK is particularly effective in addressing four key social and environmental pressures. The DST is instrumental in tackling issues such as poverty, inequality, hunger, malnutrition, and unsustainable consumption patterns. In contrast, the DTA is less effective for these specific challenges. In the District of the Sands case, the DHK plays a central role in confronting social, behavioral, and knowledge-based pressures, while the Digital Tool proves essential for ecological monitoring and diagnosing systemic issues like biodiversity loss. The DST remains a valuable resource for dealing with operational and resource-based challenges, including land degradation and water management.

3.1.4 Business model type: Agricultural production

Analysis of the usefulness of DTA in relation to social and economic barriers

DTA has decreasing influence on variable costs for four barriers: Long term results in food security, Biodiversity preservation, Regulation of water cycle and Soil quality. For the same barriers DTA increasing influence on income at the BM "Conventional and organic agriculture".

DTA has no impact on the barrier long term return.

Analysis of the contribution of digital tools to the delivery of various ecosystem services

DST and DTA have for business model "Conventional and organic agriculture" equal essential for Environmental care. DHK is not preferable for Environmental care.

DST and DTA have for business model "Conventional and organic agriculture" equal essential for Environmental care. DHK is not preferable for Environmental care.

Analysis of the toolbox for delivery of various ecosystem services according to the social preferences

DHK is preferable for four pressures at the Italian case, business model "Conventional and organic agriculture". DST is important to overcome the Poverty, inequalities, hunger and malnutrition and Inadequate diets and

unsustainable consumption patterns. DTA is not preferred for overcoming the pressures.

3.1.5 Business model type: Forest management

Analysis of the usefulness of DTA in relation to social and economic barriers

The long-term return is associated with a decrease in variable costs and no impact on income, indicating that DTA may offer strategic benefits by reducing operational expenses. In the case of sustainable crop production, there is no change in variable costs but an increase in income, suggesting that DTA can enhance profitability through better practices without significantly altering cost structures. Similarly, food demand shows no effect on variable costs but a positive impact on income, implying that DTA may help forest managers or landowners capitalize on market opportunities without increasing input requirements. Conversely, climate change presents a potential barrier, as it is linked to increased variable costs without income benefits. The regulation of the water cycle appears neutral, with no impact on either costs or income. Finally, soil quality improvements lead to increased variable costs and increased income, indicating that while DTA may require greater investment in forest soil maintenance, it can yield higher returns over time.

Analysis of the contribution of digital tools to the delivery of various ecosystem services

The DHK is the strongest overall performer, especially for natural resources protection, ecosystem resilience, and community engagement. The DST complements this with strengths in livelihoods and governance, while the DTA proves valuable in resource use and governance planning. A combined approach ensures comprehensive support for air, soil, and water quality within the CAP framework

Analysis of the toolbox for delivery of various ecosystem services according to the social preferences

DHK leads in addressing social and institutional barriers to soil health, such as poverty, behavior, and knowledge gaps. The DTA provides robust support for land and biodiversity-related pressures, while the DST is most effective in tackling environmental and infrastructural challenges.

4 Ecological and human impact of the soil health business models

4.1 Methodology

The study aims to evaluate both the ecological and human impacts of business models focused on improving soil health by conducting a Life-Cycle Analysis (LCA). The environmental and human impact are considered as one combined dimension. For the assessment, we use the carbon footprint

indicator to evaluate both environmental and human impacts. The methodological approach follows a structured process that includes the preparation of relevant data, implementation of the LCA using the FaST platform, and interpretation and reporting of results.

The process begins with the selection of a representative farm that embodies the core characteristics of the chosen soil health business model. This farm serves as a practical case for conducting the LCA and must reflect typical operations and environmental conditions relevant to the model.

Next, the soil cultivation strategy used on the selected farm must be clearly described. This includes detailing the methods for tillage and soil management, the types of crops grown and their rotation, and the use of fertilizers, amendments, and other agricultural inputs associated with the model.

To ensure an accurate LCA, several key soil quality parameters must be identified. These include the mechanical composition of the soil, sorption capacity (CEC), nutrient levels, fertilization practices (including type, quantity, and timing), expected yield levels, and irrigation needs. These variables are essential for modeling emissions and resource flows in the production process.

The FaST Navigator platform is used as the primary tool for conducting the LCA. Data entry within the platform proceeds through three phases: first, users input information related to fertilization; second, data concerning greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is entered; and third, an economic assessment is completed.

To interpret the carbon impact of each soil health business model, a specific classification scale is applied. This scale defines low impact as less than one ton of CO₂ per hectare per year, medium impact as between one and four tons, and high impact as more than four tons of CO₂ per hectare per year. This classification (Table 25) enables a comparative evaluation of the carbon footprint of each model.

Table 24: Classification Scale for Carbon Footprint Impact in Agriculture (CO₂ Emissions per Hectare per Year)

Impact Level	CO ₂ Emissions (tons/ha/year)	Description
Low	Less than 1 ton	Minimal environmental impact
Medium	1 to 4 tons	Moderate environmental impact
High	More than 4 tons	Significant environmental impact

The ecological and human impact of soil health business models will be measured using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), a standardized methodology that evaluates the environmental impacts of a product or system throughout its entire life cycle. This analysis focuses specifically on farms and does not extend to the rest of the supply chain. As a result, the carbon footprint is used

as the sole indicator, as it best reflects the environmental and human impact at the farm level.

To interpret the carbon impact of each soil health business model, a specific classification scale is applied. This scale defines low impact as less than one ton of CO₂ per hectare per year, medium impact as between one and four tons, and high impact as more than four tons of CO₂ per hectare per year.

LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) has been applied in four countries: Bulgaria, Italy, Spain, and Germany, to evaluate the ecological and human impact of different soil health business models.

In Italy, two separate farm cases were assessed. The first Italian farm from Emilia-Romagna region includes four different crops. The second Italian farm from Tuscany region focused on one crop (durum wheat) but studied under two different management strategies: conventional and organic.

In Bulgaria, one farm with a single crop (wine grapes) was evaluated. In Spain and Germany, one farm per country was included, each with a single crop.

4.2 Analysis of the results

4.2.1 Bulgaria

The farm as a part of the BM *Value chain* is in the South-Central region of Bulgaria and was established in 2022 on an area of 10 ha and is intended for growing wine grape varieties.

The creation of the vineyard is associated with the preparation of the terrain and planting material for planting an area of 10 ha; planting the vineyard and ensuring the development and protection of the newly planted vines by conducting agrotechnical and plant protection measures and building a supporting structure for the vineyard. The distance between the rows is 2.4 m, and the distance between the individual plants is 1.0 m, which makes 4170 vines / ha.

The following scheme of processing and maintaining the soil surface is observed:

- Autumn deep plowing of 20-22 cm.
- Spring plowing of 18-20 cm.
- Two to three times cultivation of the inter-rows of 8-12 cm in plantations treated with herbicides.

In vineyards not treated with herbicides, 4-5 inter-row cultivations are carried out.

Good growth, normal and regular fruiting are ensured by enough mineral and organic fertilizers. Fertilization is carried out by applying combined fertilizer /NPK/ in a ratio of 15:15:15, at a rate of 250 kg/ha. The application is carried out in the fall.

Organic fertilization is associated with the application of manure at a rate of 40,000 kg/ha.

The applied cultivation technology is associated with reducing the use of mineral fertilizers and without irrigation.

The climatic characteristics of the farm territory show that the climate is temperate continental.

The soils are represented by Luvisols (Haplic) and are characterized by an organic matter content of 1.5%. The average yield from the vineyard is 6000 kg/ha, with the export of crop residues planned.

4.2.2 Italy

The farm as a part of the BM *Collective and value chain* is in the Emilia-Romagna region of Italy and specializes in the cultivation of alfalfa. The agricultural holding covers an area of 33.12 ha, of which 5 ha are dedicated to alfalfa production. The farm operates within the field crops sector, with an economic size between €50,000 and €100,000. The farm is managed with a total labor input of 1.25 Annual Work Units (AWU) and generates a total output of €68,244, 99% of which comes from crop production.

Alfalfa is cultivated on 5 ha under rainfed conditions. The soil type is classified as Arenosol, with an organic matter content of 1.5%. The cultivation follows no-till practices, reducing disturbance and supporting soil carbon retention. The farm uses no pesticides or herbicides, and no irrigation is applied, making the system low-input and potentially more sustainable in the long term.

The nutrient management on the farm relies on minimal external input. Mineral fertilization consists of the application of superphosphate concentrate at a rate of 4 kg/ha. No nitrogen fertilizers are applied. Instead, nitrogen input is supplied entirely through natural processes—mainly soil mineralization. No organic manure is used.

Based on the data from LCA, the total greenhouse gas emissions from the alfalfa production system amount to approximately 2.32 tons of CO₂-equivalent per hectare per year. According to the established classification scale, which defines low impact as less than 1 ton, medium impact as 1 to 4 tons, and high impact as more than 4 tons of CO₂/ha/year, the farm falls into the medium impact category. This indicates a moderate environmental impact, primarily driven by the loss of soil organic carbon, which is the most significant contributor to the total emissions.

Alfalfa

The alfalfa is grown under rainfed conditions with minimal inputs. No nitrogen fertilizers are applied, and nutrient supply relies on soil mineralization and reserves. Fertilization consists only of small amounts of phosphorus (1 FU/ha) and potassium (5 FU/ha). No pesticides are used, and there is no irrigation. This system is low input and ecologically oriented

Maize

Maize is grown under irrigated conditions with a high nitrogen input: 265 kg/ha of urea is applied. No phosphorus or potassium is used, and irrigation is also applied. Crop protection includes herbicide application, and the system is intensive and yield-driven, with a production of 47,311 kg/ha

Tomato

Tomatoes are grown with heavy fertilization and irrigation. The crop receives 743 kg/ha of fertilizers, the highest among all crops. Multiple fertilizer types are used, including calcium and ammonium nitrate, urea, and potassium chloride. Crop protection is intensive, and the system is high-input and highly productive, reaching 61,450 kg/h.

Wheat (Durum)

Wheat is grown under rainfed conditions with moderate to high fertilization. It receives a total of 722 kg/ha of fertilizers. Nitrogen sources include urea and nitrogen solutions, with measurable losses via volatilization and leaching. No irrigation or insecticides are applied, but herbicides are used. The system reflects a typical intensive field crop practice

All crops are cultivated under the same farm conditions, with similar climate and soil characteristics, but their carbon footprints vary significantly depending on cultivation practices, input use, and yield.

Alfalfa has the lowest emissions (2.32 t CO₂-eq/ha), due to minimal fertilization and no pesticide use. Maize and wheat fall in the medium impact range (3.37–3.69 t CO₂-eq/ha), with emissions driven by N₂O from soils and carbon stock losses. Tomato has the highest carbon footprint (5.33 t CO₂-eq/ha), placing it in the high impact category, primarily due to intensive pesticide use and high upstream emissions from inputs.

Table 25: CO₂ impact of different case studies and crops

Crop	CO ₂ -eq (kg/ha)	Tons/ha/year	Impact Classification
Alfalfa	2318	2.32	Medium impact
Maize	3372	3.37	Medium impact
Tomato	5331	5.33	High impact
Wheat	3690	3.69	Medium impact

4.2.3 Italy 2

The farm as a part of the BM *Collective and value chain* is located in the Tuscany region of Italy and cultivates durum wheat on rainfed arable land.

The farm has a total utilized agricultural area of 16.13 ha, and its activity is oriented entirely toward field crops, with a very small livestock presence. With an economic size between €8,000 and €25,000, the farm generates a total output of €21,920, most of which comes from crop production, and operates with a total labor input of 1.11 annual work units.

The wheat cultivation system follows a conventional tillage approach, where the soil is tilled and residues are fully exported. The crop is grown under rainfed conditions, without irrigation, although a sprinkler system is installed but not in use. The soil is classified as loam, with a 1.6% organic matter content, pH of 8.5, and high cation exchange capacity (85 meq/kg), indicating a good nutrient-holding capacity.

The average grain yield is 4400 kg/ha, and the crop management follows a buildup and maintenance fertilization strategy aiming for maximum yield. A total of 550 kg/ha of fertilizers is applied, including ammonium nitrate (350 kg/ha) and di-ammonium phosphate (200 kg/ha).

The total greenhouse gas emissions amount to 1348 kg CO₂-eq/ha/year, primarily from managed soils (922 kg CO₂-eq), upstream production of inputs (130 kg), and machinery (296 kg). These values place the farm in the medium impact category based on CO₂ emissions per hectare per year (1–4 tons), indicating moderate environmental pressure, especially considering the absence of carbon sequestration and full residue export

Description of the Organic Wheat Production Strategy

The field is tilled, and no irrigation is applied despite the presence of a sprinkler system. The fertilization strategy is based on organic manure—specifically, 30,000 kg/ha of dairy cow manure—providing high nutrient inputs. This results in a total nitrogen input of 256 FU/ha when accounting for soil mineralization, biological fixation, and initial soil content. No synthetic fertilizers are used. Crop residues are retained in the system, and no insecticides or fungicides are applied; only 1 kg/ha of herbicides is used.

According to the life cycle analysis (LCA), the organic wheat system emits 1,702 kg CO₂-eq/ha/year. This places it in the medium impact category (1–4 tons/ha/year). Compared to the conventional wheat system (same region, same crop), which emits 1,348 kg CO₂-eq/ha, the organic model emits 26% more greenhouse gases. While the organic approach avoids synthetic fertilizers, the higher nitrogen losses from manure (especially volatilization and leaching) contribute to increased N₂O emissions—a gas with much higher global warming potential than CO₂.

Additionally, the yield in the organic system is slightly lower (4100 kg/ha vs. 4400 kg/ha), which increases the CO₂-eq per ton of product from 306 kg CO₂-eq/t to 415 kg CO₂-eq/t.

4.2.4 Spain

The farm as a part of the BM *Value chain* is located in the Andalusia region of southern Spain and specializes in irrigated olive production.

The farm covers a total utilized agricultural area of 14.91 hectares, with olive trees cultivated on 10 hectares under a drip irrigation system. The farm operates within the “other permanent crops” classification and has an economic size of €8,000–25,000. It employs a total labor input of 1.04 AWU

(Annual Work Units) and achieves a total farm output of €36,615, nearly all of which derives from olive cultivation

The olive grove yields an average of 3,500 kg/ha, and production is fully mechanized and tilled. The sandy loam soil (franco arenoso) is moderately fertile, with a pH of 7, high cation exchange capacity (120 meq/kg), and 1.5% organic matter content. The climate is warm temperate dry, and annual rainfall reaches 800 mm, supplemented by 2,500 m³/ha of irrigation water per year

The fertilization strategy follows a “sufficiency” approach with minimum input to maintain yield. A compound NPK fertilizer (15-15-15) is applied at a rate of 400 kg/ha. Nutrient sources also include nitrogen from soil reserves (30 FU/ha), mineralization (30 FU/ha), and irrigation water (122 FU/ha). Nutrient use efficiency is moderate: nitrogen uptake is 54 FU/ha, with leaching losses of 29 FU/ha and volatilization of 2 FU/ha. The phosphorus uptake is around 10 FU/ha, while potassium uptake was not recorded despite its presence in the fertilization plan

The greenhouse gas emissions from the olive system total 1,670 kg CO₂-eq/ha/year, composed of direct and indirect soil emissions (392 kg CO₂-eq/ha), upstream input production (105 kg), machinery (3 kg), and a substantial contribution from losses in soil carbon stock (1,170 kg CO₂-eq/ha). According to the carbon footprint classification scale, this places the farm in the medium impact category (1–4 tons CO₂-eq/ha/year), indicating moderate environmental pressure.

4.2.5 Germany

The farm as a part of the BM *Agricultural Production/ Value chain* is located in a cool temperate moist climate region and focuses on soft bread wheat production.

The crop is grown on 1 hectare of Cambisol soil, characterized by 1.5% soil organic matter and conventional tillage practices that transitioned to no-till three years ago. The system does not apply cover crops, manure, compost, or organic matter amendments. All crop residues are incorporated into the soil. The average wheat yield is 8,000 kg/ha, and the field is rainfed, with no irrigation or drainage interventions

Wheat is grown using 160 kg/ha of seed and weed and disease control involves the application of 1 kg/ha each of herbicides and fungicides, along with 1 kg/ha of other plant protection treatments. Fuel consumption reaches 74 liters of diesel per hectare, indicating a mechanized production system. The farm practices moderate nutrient management, with nitrogen leaching at 29.98 kg/ha and volatilization losses at 11.55 kg/ha, suggesting room for improving nitrogen efficiency.

Total greenhouse gas emissions from the system reach 2,903 kg CO₂-eq/ha/year, distributed across: direct and indirect soil emissions (N₂O): 1,746 kg

CO₂-eq/ha, upstream emissions from inputs (fertilizers, pesticides, seeds): 907 kg CO₂-eq/ha, machinery emissions: 252 kg CO₂-eq/ha

This places the system in the medium carbon impact category (1–4 tons CO₂-eq/ha/year), reflecting moderate environmental pressure, primarily due to nitrogen-related emissions and upstream production of fertilizers and agrochemicals.

4.3 Conclusion Based on CO₂ Emissions Across Countries and Production Systems

The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) results from five different farms across Italy, Spain, Germany, and Bulgaria highlight the central role of agricultural practices in shaping carbon emissions per hectare. Despite diverse crops, climates, and farm structures, all systems fall within the medium carbon impact category—defined as 1 to 4 tons CO₂-equivalent per hectare per year. However, the drivers of emissions and the efficiency of systems vary widely.

Italy – Farm 1 (Multiple Crops), BM type *Collective and value chain*

Among the four crops analyzed, alfalfa stands out with the lowest emissions (2.32 t CO₂-eq/ha) due to its low-input, no-till, and rainfed system with no nitrogen fertilizer. In contrast, tomato production reaches 5.33 t CO₂-eq/ha, placing it in the high impact category, primarily because of intensive input use—particularly fertilizers and pesticides. Maize (3.37 t) and wheat (3.69 t) remain in the medium category but are relatively high due to N₂O emissions and lack of carbon sequestration.

Italy – Farm 2 (Wheat, Conventional vs. Organic), BM type *Collective and value chain*

Both the conventional (1.35 t CO₂-eq/ha) and organic (1.70 t CO₂-eq/ha) systems fall into the medium impact range, but organic emits ~26% more. Despite the absence of synthetic inputs, the organic model produces more N₂O due to manure-related nitrogen losses. Moreover, lower yield in the organic system results in a higher emission intensity per ton of product (415 vs. 306 kg CO₂-eq/t).

Spain – Olive Production, BM type *Value chain*

The Spanish olive system also falls into the medium impact category at 1.67 t CO₂-eq/ha/year. While irrigation and fertilization are applied, overall emissions remain moderate. However, losses of soil organic carbon (1.17 t CO₂-eq/ha) are the largest contributor, revealing a risk to long-term sustainability if soil health is not maintained.

Germany – Wheat (No-Till System), BM type *Agricultural production/value chain*

Despite reduced tillage and residue incorporation, the German wheat system emits 2.90 t CO₂-eq/ha/year, mostly due to high nitrogen-related emissions and upstream input production. This illustrates that even modern, mechanized systems with conservation practices can have notably high emissions if nitrogen efficiency is low.

Bulgaria – Vineyard, BM type *Value chain*

In contrast to all other farms, the Bulgarian vineyard exhibits a net negative carbon footprint from land-use change, sequestering 3.7 t CO₂-eq/ha/year, making it a carbon sink. This is due to perennial vegetation, lack of irrigation, and high organic matter input (manure), suggesting strong potential for carbon-neutral or even climate-positive agriculture under the right conditions.

While all systems are within the medium emissions range (1–4 t CO₂-eq/ha), they vary greatly in efficiency and climate impact per unit of output. Systems like alfalfa and vineyards show strong carbon performance, while crops like tomato and high-input wheat demonstrate greater emissions per hectare and per ton. This highlights the importance of tailoring management practices—especially regarding nitrogen and soil carbon—to minimize the carbon footprint of agriculture while maintaining productivity.

5 Feedback from CoP

5.1 Methodology

For the analysis of the feedback from CoP was created a instruction that gives information to CoP about the digital solutions in NOVASOIL toolbox, summary of the results from testing and valorisation considering national specificities, business models and case studies. The CoP members in each NOVASOIL partner country fulfilled a short survey for evaluation NOVASOIL toolbox. WP3 will collect internal feedback of the solutions and case studies evaluated in NOVASOIL reporting on perceived usefulness of the soil health business models, cost of implementation in relation to the characteristics of the different land uses (e.g. agriculture, forestry, urban areas), delivering suggestions of final refinements as well as policy relevant feedback.

Each case study in NOVASOIL project and respective partners will be responsible for delivering the information required for the feedback from CoP.

The list of the case studies are as follows:

Table 26: List of the case studies

Nº	Country	Name	Business model type
1	Spain	Integrated production	Value chain
2	Spain	Organic wine in Rueda, Spain (Rueda)	Value chain
3	Bulgaria	Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism	Value chain

4	Italy	District of the Sands - Emilia-Romagna	Collective and value chain
5	Italy	A model for multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas - Tuscany Region	Collective and value chain
6	Italy	CiRAA LTEs on conventional and organic agriculture	Agricultural production
7	Latvia	Crop production and animal farming	Value chain
8	Germany	CO2-Land	Agricultural production/value chain
9	Latvia		Forestry

Within the document, we have aggregated and analyzed the information received from partners during the valorization process of the digital tools.

This information is first systematized by a type of business model. Second, for each business model, we provide:

1. Analysis of the usefulness of DTA in relation to social and economic barriers;
2. Analysis of the contribution of digital tools from the toolbox to the delivery of various ecosystem services
3. Analysis of the toolbox for delivery of various ecosystem services according to social preferences.

The CoP members in each NOVASOIL partner country have to fulfil the survey for NOVASOIL toolbox evaluation (Annex 1).

5.2 Analysis

The purpose of the internal feedback is to gather in-depth insight of the solutions and case studies assessed within NOVASOIL, focusing on the perceived value and practical relevance of the soil health business models and proposed digital solutions. It will evaluate the cost and feasibility of implementation, considering the specific characteristics of different land uses—such as agriculture, forestry, and urban environments. The insights will provide targeted, policy-relevant recommendations to support future uptake and integration into land management strategies.

The survey was answered by CoP in Bulgaria, Estonia, Italy (Emilia Romagna Region), Italy (Tuscany Region), Spain, France, and Germany.

Table 28 gives a summary of the responses to “Is the proposed Toolbox easy to understand?”

Table 27: Summary of the responses to “Is the proposed Toolbox easy to understand?”

Country / Region	DHK	DTA	DST
Italy – Emilia-Romagna	Yes	Yes	No

Italy – Tuscany	Yes	(No answer)	No
Bulgaria	Yes	No	No
Estonia	Yes	No	No
Germany	Yes	No access	No
France	Yes	Yes	Yes

DHK is generally well understood across all countries, with all respondents answering "Yes". DTA received mixed feedback, with several countries (Bulgaria, Estonia, and no access in Germany) indicating difficulty or inability to evaluate it, a problem that have been resolved. DST is the most frequently rated as "Not easy to understand", with only France giving it full approval.

Table 29 is a summarized table of the responses to – “Do you find the Toolbox useful for soil health business models?”

Table 28: Summary of the responses to “Do you find the Toolbox useful for soil health business models?”

Country / Region	DHK	DTA	DST
Italy – Emilia-Romagna	Yes	Yes	Yes
Italy – Tuscany	No	(No answer)	No
Bulgaria	Yes	Yes	Yes
Estonia	Yes and No	No – unclear purpose	Maybe – depending on data availability
Germany	Yes	No access	No
France	Yes	Yes	Yes

DHK is seen as useful by most countries, though Estonia expresses mixed opinions and Italy (Tuscany) rated it as not useful. DTA received positive feedback from France, Italy (Emilia-Romagna), and Bulgaria, but negative or unclear responses from Estonia, and no access reported by Germany. DST was viewed as useful by most, but Italy (Tuscany) and Germany found it not useful, and Estonia was undecided, depending on data availability.

Table 30 gives a summary of the responses to the question – “Do you understand the goal of the Toolbox?”

Table 29: Summary of the responses to “Do you understand the goal of the Toolbox?”

Country / Region	DHK	DTA	DST
Italy – Emilia-Romagna	Yes	Yes	Yes
Italy – Tuscany	No	(No answer)	Yes
Bulgaria	Yes	No	No

Estonia	Yes – “Helps promote soil health BMs”	No – tool unclear, issues	Yes, but clarification needed
Germany	Yes	No access	No
France	Yes	Yes	Yes

DHK is generally well understood, except by Italy (Tuscany). DTA received critical feedback from Estonia and was not understood by Bulgaria. DST was least understood in Bulgaria and Germany, and Estonia suggested it needs to offer more actionable guidance. Overall, while the general goals of the Toolbox are clear to most, DTA and DST require improvements in clarity, guidance, and user orientation, especially for technical or less digitally fluent audiences.

Table 31 gives a summary of the responses to question – “*Is the Toolbox generally easy and intuitive to use?*”

Table 30: Summary of the responses to “Is the Toolbox generally easy and intuitive to use?”

Country / Region	DHK	DTA	DST
Italy – Emilia-Romagna	Yes	Yes	No
Italy – Tuscany	No	<i>(No answer)</i>	No
Bulgaria	Yes	No	No
Estonia	Yes <i>(needs translation)</i>	No <i>(multiple usability issues)</i>	No <i>(needs major clarification)</i>
Germany	No	No access	Yes
France	Yes	No	No

DHK is generally seen as the most user-friendly, although France and Germany reported usability issues, and Estonia emphasized the need for language localization. DTA received the most negative feedback, especially regarding technical glitches (log-in, data loss, unclear results grid). DST is viewed as unclear and unintuitive by most respondents, with France, Bulgaria, Estonia, and Italy (Tuscany) all noting difficulties; only Germany found it intuitive.

These findings highlight a clear need to improve interface usability, provide clearer terminology, localize content, and ensure functional reliability, especially for DTA and DST.

Table 32 gives Average Usefulness Rating by Tool Across Each Business Model from question 6

Table 31: Average Usefulness Rating by Tool Across Each Business Model

Business Model	DHK	DTA	DST

Value chain	2.33	3.67	2.8
Collective and value chain	2.67	3.33	2.8
Agricultural production	2.83	4	3.4
Agricultural prod/value chain	2.67	4	3
Forestry	2.17	3.33	3

DTA shows the highest average usefulness across all business models, especially in agricultural contexts (4.00 in both “Agricultural production” and “Agri-prod/value chain”). This confirms that DTA is the most effective tool for cost optimization in soil-related decisions when well understood.

DST performs consistently in the medium range, especially for agricultural production (3.40), reflecting a good fit with crop-level decisions. However, its performance is slightly weaker in collective and value chain contexts, indicating a need for better contextual guidance and clarity.

DHK remains the least effective across all models, with the lowest score in forestry (2.17). This suggests that while DHK provides foundational knowledge, it is perceived as less directly actionable, especially for specialized applications like forestry. Enhancing its relevance through tailored content or interactive elements could increase its utility.

Here is the summary of the comments from question 7 from the survey:

DTA and DST are promising but require simplification, better interface design, and farmer-oriented language.

DHK needs clearer content classification, better navigation, and more direct value for decision-making.

There is a strong consensus on the value of integrating the toolbox into policy, education, and practical demonstration projects.

Several countries call for capacity building and user support, highlighting the digital divide as a barrier to wider adoption.

5.3. Conclusions

The NOVASOIL Toolbox, comprising three digital tools (DHK, DTA, and DST), was evaluated across several countries to assess its clarity, usability, practical value, and policy relevance. Overall, the feedback highlights the promising potential of these tools to support soil health practices, while also offering valuable suggestions for refinement and broader adoption.

Understanding and Clarity

DHK is widely understood and valued for its solid foundational content. Stakeholders across different countries appreciated its informative character, although some noted the need for more tailored guidance for specific sectors

like forestry and horticulture. DTA, while recognized as highly beneficial in supporting soil-health decision-making, received mixed feedback on clarity—mainly due to its complexity and access limitations reported in some countries, problems that have been resolved. DST was less well understood, especially by those with less technical expertise. It was noted that the tool contains complex terminology and detailed data requirements that may overwhelm some users. With better contextual explanations and user-oriented design, both DTA and DST have strong potential to become more accessible and impactful.

Usability and Accessibility

DHK stands out as the most user-friendly of the three, although improvements in content navigation, classification, and format labeling would make it even more effective. DTA, despite being highly valued when accessible, was hampered by technical issues such as login difficulties, loss of data, and unclear result displays - problems that have been resolved. DST was often considered too advanced for general users, due to its data-heavy interface and technical language. Across the board, users suggested enhancing usability through simpler interfaces, clearer instructions, multilingual support, and more intuitive navigation. Addressing these points will significantly improve the user experience, particularly for farmers and practitioners with limited digital skills.

Usefulness for Soil Health Business Models

DTA emerged as the most practically useful tool, receiving the highest average usefulness ratings across all business model categories—especially in agricultural production contexts. This reflects its strong alignment with decision-making needs in soil management, provided that access and understanding barriers are addressed. DST demonstrated moderate effectiveness, particularly at the field level, though it was seen as less suited for broader value chain or forestry applications. DHK, while informative, was rated lower in terms of direct applicability, indicating a need to link its content more closely with on-the-ground decision-making. These findings show that all three tools offer distinct strengths, and with targeted improvements, they can serve as complementary components in a comprehensive soil health support system.

Policy and Implementation Potential

There is a strong consensus across participating countries on the strategic importance of incorporating the Toolbox into national and EU-level agricultural policies. Recommendations included using the tools to inform CAP-related subsidies, feasibility studies for farmers, and evaluations of advisory services. Additionally, there was a shared call for embedding the tools in agricultural education and professional training to foster digital literacy and long-term soil stewardship. Pilot projects, demonstration farms, and policy alignment were suggested as key steps to scale the tools and support uptake.

Final Reflection

The NOVASOIL Toolbox offers a robust digital framework to advance soil health through evidence-based decision-making. While the tools show strong promise, especially DTA, achieving widespread adoption will require further refinement. Key areas for improvement include simplifying user interfaces, offering clearer contextual guidance, supporting capacity-building efforts, and ensuring full integration with policy frameworks. With these adjustments, the Toolbox is well-positioned to evolve from a promising innovation to a widely used, scalable solution for sustainable soil management across Europe.

6 Conclusions

The testing and valorisation of the NOVASOIL toolbox across multiple European contexts provide clear evidence that digital solutions can significantly contribute to overcoming barriers in soil health business models.

Main conclusions:

1. **Complementary role of tools:** The three instruments serve different but complementary functions. DTA excels in **economic optimisation**, DST in **strategic and operational planning**, and DHK in **knowledge transfer and social engagement**. Their integrated use is essential to maximise impact.
2. **Economic and environmental synergies:** Case studies demonstrated that SHBMs can reduce costs and increase income while delivering positive ecological outcomes. Vineyards in Bulgaria and olive systems in Spain illustrate how soil-oriented practices can achieve **climate-smart outcomes** when properly managed.
3. **Cross-country variability:** Results confirm that context matters — input-intensive systems (e.g., tomatoes in Italy) face higher CO₂ footprints, while perennial or low-input systems offer better sustainability performance. This underlines the need for **tailored SHBMs** adapted to national and regional conditions.
4. **Stakeholder acceptance:** CoP feedback confirms that the NOVASOIL tools are perceived as useful and relevant for practice, but greater efforts are needed to **simplify interfaces, improve digital literacy, and provide demonstration projects** to accelerate adoption.
5. **Policy relevance:** The tools have strong potential to be integrated into CAP monitoring frameworks, eco-schemes, and carbon farming schemes. Their use could improve transparency, support evidence-based policy, and strengthen farmer engagement in soil stewardship.

The NOVASOIL toolbox is a practical and scalable innovation that can bridge science, policy, and practice. By combining economic, ecological, and social perspectives, it offers a solid foundation for building resilient, climate-positive, and inclusive soil health business models across Europe.

Resources

1. Nikolov D., Tzvetanova E., Boevsky I., Banov M., Kostenarov K., Todorova K. (2023b) NOVASOIL D3.2 Preliminary version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models
2. Nikolov D., Tzvetanova E., Boevsky I., Banov M., Kostenarov K., Marinova, Ts. (2023a) NOVASOIL D3.1 – Report on mapping existing incentives for sustainable soil health business models
3. Garrett, L. and Neves, B. (2016) Incentives for Ecosystem Services: Spectrum. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, Italy
4. Compagno, L., D'Urso, D., Latora, A. G., Trapani, N. (2013). The Value-Analytic Hierarchy Process: A Lean Multi Criteria Decision Support Method. Manufacturing Modelling, Management and Control, 7(1), 875-880. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3182/20130619-3-RU-3018.00573>
5. Nikolov D., Tzvetanova E., Boevsky I., Banov M., Kostenarov K., Todorova K. (2024b) NOVASOIL D 3.5 Report on final version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models
6. Nikolov D., Tzvetanova E., Boevsky I., Banov M., Kostenarov K., Bankova V. (2025) NOVASOIL D 3.8 Report on final version of tools for analysis of the soil health business models

Acknowledgment

Annexes

Annex 1

Survey for NOVASOIL toolbox evaluation.

I. General information

1. Name:

II. Feedback on proposed Toolbox

2. Is the proposed Toolbox easy to understand?

DTs/Business models	Yes/no
DHK	
DTA	
DST	

3. Do you find the toolbox useful for soil health business models?

DTs/Business models	Yes/no
DHK	
DTA	
DST	

III. Toolbox evaluation

4. Do you understand the goal of Toolbox?

DTs/Business models	Yes/no
DHK	
DTA	
DST	

5. Is the Toolbox generally easy and intuitive to use?

DTs/Business models	Yes/no
DHK	
DTA	
DST	

6. Please answer the following questions: How useful is the toolbox in minimizing the cost of supply by implementing soil health business models? Use the scale from 1 to 5, as 1 - Unsatisfactory, 2 - Satisfactory, 3 - Good, 4 - Very Good, 5 - Excellent

DTs/Business models	Value chain	Collective and value chain	Agricultural production	Agricultural production/value chain	Forestry
DHK					
DTA					
DST					

7. Do you have any policy relevant suggestions for how the results from the Toolbox could be used to support soil health business model?

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